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iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

D2_1 – Enhanced Safety Criteria Catalogue (SCC) for urban and secondary roads

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ABOUT iDRIVING

iDriving, a 3-year Horizon-funded project, unites 17 European partners in a mission to enhance road safety_ The project focuses on transforming urban and secondary rural road infrastructure through innovation_ It aligns with the EU's goals for smart transport and actively embraces emerging technologies_ Key areas of impact include enhancing driver behaviour, improving infrastructure safety, and empowering first responders_ Through a comprehensive Safety Criteria Catalogue, innovative sensors, AI-based warnings, and a Digital Twin, iDriving paves the way for safer roads_

The iDriving consortium consists of the following partners:

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1	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
2	POLYTECHNEIO KRITIS	TUC	EL
3	AUSTRIATECH - GESELLSCHAFT DES BUNDES FUR AT TECHNOLOGIEPOLITISCHE MASSNAHMEN GMBH	AUSTRIATECH	AT
4	UNIVERSITE GUSTAVE EIFFEL	UNI_EIFFEL	FR
5	FUNDACION TEKNIKER	TEKNIKER	ES
6	INGARTEK CONSULTING SL	ING	ES

7	INFRA PLAN KONZALTNIG JDOO ZA USLUGE	INFRA PLAN	HR
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Glossary

AU	Alcohol Usage
AEB	Autonomous Emergency Braking
AED	Automated External Defibrillator
AID	Automatic Incident Detection
BAC	Blood Alcohol Content
CARE	Community database on Accidents on the Roads in Europe
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CRSU	Child Restraint System Usage
DU	Drug Usage
EC	European Commission
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
ESS	Environmental Sensor Stations
EU	European Union
EuroNCAP	European New Car Assessment Programme
IMS	Incident Management Systems
ISA	Intelligent Speed Assistance
ISAD	Infrastructure Classification Scheme for Automated Driving
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MAIS	Maximum abbreviated injury scale
MDis	Mobile device Distraction
NOC	Network operational centre
PASER	Pavement Surface Evaluation and Rating

PET	Post Encroachment Time
PCC	Post Crash Care
RWIS	Road Weather Information Systems
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SBU	Safety belt Usage
SCC	Safety Criteria Catalogue
SLC	Speed limit compliance
SMM	Speed Management Measure
SSM	Surrogate Safety Measures
SZW	School zone Warning
THW	Time Headway
TM	Traffic management
TLS _{viol}	Traffic Light Signal Violation
TTC	Time To Collision
UC	Use Case
V2I	Vehicle to Infrastructure
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
WAS	Warning alert System
WtAS	Weather alert System

Executive summary

In this report, the enhanced Safety Criteria Catalogue (SCC) for the assessment of safety on secondary and urban roads is presented, as a result of work performed within Task 2.1. Firstly, thorough literature review was performed, then interviews with partners participating in WP2, followed by the workshops with the whole consortium during GA meetings in Graz (February 2025) and Paris (September 2025). Continuous feedback from the end-users was incorporated to tailor the KPIs to the specific needs of secondary and urban road networks and implementation of digital technologies. The approach for the development of the iDriving Safety Criteria Catalogue (SCC) was to analyse the safety on roads holistically with integrated ISAD concept, as a result of an interactive system consisting of multiple components and actors involved.

The main purpose of the enhanced SCC is to provide a methodology for the evaluation of digital technologies implementation and monitoring systems, such as deployed in the iDriving pilots, and to offer reference for other Vision-Zero initiatives. The SCC framework is a holistic framework, which integrates four categories, namely road users, vehicles, infrastructure, communication and traffic management, into one system. The road users category relies on the concept developed within the BASELINE project, within which eight categories of KPIs for evaluating road users safety are proposed, incl. speeding, seatbelt and child restraint use, protective equipment use, alcohol influence, mobile device distraction, vehicle safety, infrastructure, and post-crash care. For the other three categories related to the vehicles, communication and traffic management and infrastructure, KPIs are based on the relevant standards, ISAD classification system and integration of digital technologies for data collection, monitoring and communication systems. The SCC defines KPIs linked to safety criteria, for example, speed limit compliance that are implemented through one or more specific indicators (i.e., “% of road users-cars travelling within the speed limit”). Within the iDriving platform continuous inputs from different tools and monitoring systems will be incorporated and translated into KPIs (Task 5.1) for specific needs of secondary and urban road networks.

The novel concept of proposed SCC KPIs is that they are tailored to the holistic approach of analysing road system and real-time data integration, AI-driven analytics, and dynamic KPI based safety evaluation and visualization, which will be demonstrated in 6 iDriving pilots. Tangible societal benefits such as the reduction of collisions, lowering of maintenance costs, and alleviation of traffic congestion are aimed to be achieved through the usage of dynamic safety KPIs.

1 Introduction

The EU's road safety agenda aims for near-zero fatalities and serious injuries by 2050, with an in between goal to halve both fatalities and serious injuries by 2030 using 2020 as the baseline, treating road deaths as unacceptable. At the heart of this agenda is the Safe System approach, which accepts that collisions will happen but insists deaths and serious injuries are avoidable by building layered protections, safer vehicles, safer roads, lower speeds and improved post-crash care, so that when one element fails others compensate (EC, 2020). To turn it into action the Framework's recommendations focus on mobilising EU and national finance, mandating vehicle safety technologies such as Intelligent Speed Assistance (ISA) and Autonomous Emergency Braking (AEB), automatic braking to avoid or mitigate collisions), supporting speed-limit databases for city deployment of ISA, improving cross-border enforcement of traffic offences, and strengthening EU-level coordination, monitoring and technical capacity (Expert Group for Urban Mobility, 2024). The policy presented above, builds upon the 2018 Strategic Action Plan (EC, 2018), which set the roadmap for implementing Vision Zero. The preparatory methodological work defines what makes a usable KPI: a clear quantitative definition, guidance on how to measure and what to count, a baseline and sampling rules, and it warns about data gaps and differences between countries in how data are collected (Silverans & Vanhove, 2023). Independent benchmarking shows large differences in road safety performance between countries, and it shows that Key Performance Indicator (KPI) monitoring combined with effective policy produces measurable safety gains, high-performing countries offer practical models of comprehensive action and systematic KPI use (European Transport Safety Council, 2025). Expert briefs for 2024–2029 call for a focus on active travel and vulnerable users, rapid updating of vehicle safety standards, and improved enforcement and data sharing, these priorities imply refining and extending KPI scopes to capture new risks and measures (Mustapha et al., 2024).

To adequately address the complex landscape of safety issues in urban or secondary roads in Europe, a comprehensive solution, a platform prototype, is being developed within iDriving project, which is highly flexible, adaptable, and capable of real-time adjustments, alongside with holistic Safety Criteria Catalogue. Safety Criteria Catalogue (SCC) is multi-layered framework, covering four dimensions of the road transport system, road users, vehicles, traffic management and communication, and transport infrastructure, which will be integrated into digital ecosystem, enhanced with sensor data and real-time data integration, AI-driven analytics, and dynamic KPI based safety evaluation. KPIs are tailored to the recent needs of secondary and urban road networks, such as roads readiness assessment for autonomous vehicles, in line with ISAD classification.

The visualization of SCC KPIs is enabled in the iDriving platform, which will ensure that the solutions are more effective in reducing fatalities and enhancing road

safety by shaping desirable road user behaviour. The enhanced SCC establishes a benchmark for safety standards and KPIs, forming the foundational blueprint that guides the identification and assessment of hazards, the implementation of mitigating measures, and the provision of alerts to all road users.

The report is structured as follows: Chapter 2 begins with a comprehensive literature review, including a brief overview on EU-policy documents, relevant EU projects and other literature. Chapter 3 introduces the methodology for development of multi-layered Safety Criteria Catalogue. Chapter 4 is explaining each of the four categories (road users, vehicles, traffic management and communication, road infrastructure), and relevance for iDriving project. Chapter 5 is providing SCC catalogue of KPI cards, where within the KPI card the definition, metric and link to the relevant standard are provided. The final Chapter 6 provides deliverable conclusions and outlook to the future work.

2 Literature review

For the majority of the 20th century, road safety was organized around 3 E's, Engineering, Education & Enforcement. Engineering designed infrastructure. Education created safe drivers. Enforcement disciplined non-compliant road users (Toole Design, 2021). This segmented approach relied on the assumption that road users could be taught and disciplined to always follow the rules. It presumed systematic safety measures in infrastructure, vehicles and traffic management are unnecessary because driver compliance would prevent accidents. It expected them to never err, therefore creating a "perfect" human (Belin et al., 2012). As a consequence, because infrastructure was presumed to be correct, collisions were attributed to individual human errors rather than the system as a whole. This model placed the entire weight of dangers of participating in traffic on the human. It overlooked that humans inevitably make mistakes and that system should be designed to prevent these errors from causing death or injury (Trafikverket, 2019).

Limitations of the 3 E safety framework, which relies solely on driver compliance, set the stage for a paradigm shift. In 1997, the Swedish Parliament established a new strategy to road safety, Vision Zero. Its long-term goal is that no one should be killed or seriously injured in road traffic (Trafikverket, 2019). This shift in attitude was formalized in Tylösand Declaration which established that "Everyone has the right to use roads and streets without threats to life or health" (Swedish Road Administration, 1997). Rather than relying only on individual compliance and behaviour in traffic, Vision Zero shifts the ultimate responsibility to the system designers to anticipate and accommodate for human errors (European Commission, 2018). It introduced the concept of layered protection, where if one layer fails to prevent the accident, another layer would compensate and mitigate the effects. Under this "Safe System" approach, the focus shifts from just preventing

crashes to managing them. It aims to reduce the forces impacting the road users during the crash to remain below physical tolerance levels of the human body (European Commission, 2023).

Despite the introduction of Vision Zero, EU progress on implementing it was inconsistent, although it showed early success. The initial target that was set in 2001 to halve the road deaths by 2010 was almost met, achieving a 43 % reduction. But the subsequent decade saw a change in pace. The goal was yet again to halve road deaths, however by 2018 deaths have fallen by only 21 %. This lack of progress can be attributed to economic recovery which increased transport usage along with cuts to transport police and infrastructure maintenance budgets (Adminaité-Fodor et al., 2019).

To address this stagnation, a new policy direction was needed. The Valletta Declaration (2017) is a pivotal agreement on road safety that drew attention to the reduction of serious injuries alongside the continued efforts to lower fatalities, specifically by establishing a reliable and comparable common definition based on the Maximum abbreviated injury scale (MAIS)(Ministerial Declaration on Road Safety, 2017). The EU has set a target to halve the number of fatalities and serious injuries by 2030 and committed to a long-term “Vision Zero” goal of eliminating road fatalities entirely by 2050. It will try to achieve its goals by implementing the Safe System approach, monitoring progress through specific key performance indicators. The year 2020 is set as a baseline not just because it marks another decade of measurement, but because it serves as the starting reference using this new common definition within the overall strategy framework (European Commission, 2018).

To track the progress, EU initiated the BASELINE Project (2020-2022). It recognised that current statistics of road accidents are “lagging indicators” in a way that they only track when failure is an outcome. To effectively manage road safety under the Safe System approach, it was necessary to measure “leading indicators”, behaviours and states that preceded crashes (European Commission, 2019).

Project resulted in 8 core KPIs which are:

1. Speed: Percentage of vehicles travelling within the legal speed limit.
2. Safety Belts & Restraints: Percentage of vehicle occupants using safety belts or child restraint systems correctly.
3. Protective Equipment: Percentage of riders of powered two-wheelers and bicycles wearing protective helmets.
4. Alcohol: Percentage of drivers driving within the legal limit for blood alcohol content (BAC).
5. Distraction: Percentage of drivers not using a handheld mobile device.
6. Vehicle Safety: Percentage of new passenger cars with a Euro NCAP safety rating equal or above a defined threshold.

7. Infrastructure: Percentage of distance driven on roads with a safety rating above a defined threshold.
8. Post-Crash Care: Time elapsed between the emergency call following a collision and the arrival of the emergency services at the scene. (Baseline Project, 2022).

Despite the clarity of KPIs, translating these measurements into comparable and actionable data proved to be a problem. Major obstacle was that national data was often incomparable. To solve the problem, project enforced harmonization, by requiring clear quantitative definitions and representative sampling instead of just simple administrative data. This ensured that each indicator meant the same thing in all countries that participated (European Commission / SWOV, 2018). Benchmarking revealed that effort is linked to results. Countries that monitored these KPIs systematically achieved measurable safety gains and therefore proving that data-guided policy saves lives (European Transport Safety Council, 2025). However, significant blind spot remains. While major networks are well-tracked, secondary and non-primary roads display distinct crash patterns and persistent data gaps. This overlooks the specific dangers of rural networks where many fatalities still occur. National averages mask local spatial variations. International databases like CARE use broad categories which miss the specific risk of secondary & interurban road networks. Fatalities on secondary roads account for 21 % in Netherlands and up to 48 % in Portugal. Monitoring these networks is technologically challenging because of the financial cost of high-fidelity sensors which are unviable for such low-traffic networks. As a result, secondary roads usually lack the digital tools for advanced monitoring, and they rely on infrequent visual inspections (FERSI, 2020).

The Infrastructure Support for Automated Driving (ISAD) classification scheme, developed under INFRAMIX project (Carreras et al., 2018) has the aim to categorize to what extent can a road's infrastructure support automated and connected vehicles (AVs/CAVs). ISAD levels are intended to be applied segment-by-segment rather than to an entire network as a whole. This recognizes that infrastructure support can vary significantly along different parts of a road or highway. The classification, presented in Table 2-1, helps road operators identify which parts of the network which are already suitable for certain automated driving functions, which need targeted upgrades, and which could support higher levels of service for CAVs. iDriving SCC has therefore integrated ISAD concept within SCC framework and linked to the digital information, monitoring and sensing data, communication systems and operative services that support traffic and infrastructure decision making.

Table 2-1 Overview of ISAD levels (Carreras et al.,2018)

	Level	Name	Description	Digital information provided to AVs			
				Digital map with static	VMS, warnings, incidents, weather	Microscopic traffic situation	Guidance: speed, gap, lane, advice
Conventional Infrastructure	E	Conventional Infrastructure / no AV support	Conventional infrastructure without digital information. AVs need to recognise road geometry and road signs.				
	D	Static Digital Information / Map support	Digital map data is available with static road signs. Map data could be complemented by physical reference points (landmarks signs). Traffic lights, short term road works and VMS need to be recognized by AVs.	X			
Digital Infrastructure	C	Dynamic Digital Information	All dynamic and static infrastructure information is available in digital form and can be provided to AVs.	X	X		
	B	Cooperative Perception	Infrastructure is capable of perceiving microscopic traffic situations and providing this data to AVs in realtime.	X	X	X	
	A	Cooperative Driving	Based on the real-time information on vehicle movements, the infrastructure is able to guide AVs (groups of vehicles or single vehicles) in order to optimize the overall traffic flow.	X	X	X	X

As outlined in Vision Zero and the Baseline project, clear policy objectives and harmonized key performance indicators (KPIs) have been established to track road safety performance, shifting the focus from individual road user behavior toward a holistic, system-based approach supported by leading safety indicators. Despite these advances, important challenges remain. Data collection practices still differ across countries, monitoring of secondary and low-traffic roads is limited, and high-risk locations as well as vulnerable road users in both rural and urban areas are frequently underrepresented. These gaps highlight the need for a structured and scalable assessment framework capable of capturing safety-relevant criteria across all dimensions of road infrastructure within a single, coherent catalogue. In this context, this deliverable presents a comprehensive proposal of safety criteria catalogue with defined KPIs four dimensions, which will be demonstrated and validated across 6 Use Cases in iDriving project.

3 Methodology

The approach for the development of the iDriving Safety Criteria Catalogue (SCC) was to analyse the safety on roads holistically, as a result of an interactive system consisting of multiple components and actors involved, namely road users, vehicles, road infrastructure and traffic management and communication system. To formulate the Safety Criteria Catalogue (SCC) several co-creation workshops were organized during which the KPIs for each SCC category were presented and discussed. The main purpose of the enhanced SCC was to develop methodology for the evaluation of implementation of digital technologies and monitoring systems, such as in the iDriving pilots, and to offer reference for other Vision-Zero initiatives. The SCC defines KPIs linked to safety criteria, for example, speed limit compliance that are implemented through one or more specific indicators (i.e., “% of road users-cars travelling within the speed limit”). Within the iDriving platform continuous inputs from different tools and monitoring systems will be incorporated to tailor the KPIs to the specific needs of secondary and urban road networks. Ongoing measurement, determination and visualization of KPIs, and analysis of road safety metrics is in this way enabled.

Table 3-1 Overview of Safety Criteria Catalogue categories

Category	ROAD USERS	VEHICLES	TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT AND COMMUNICATION	INFRASTRUCTURE
Subcategory	Speed limit compliance Safety belt Protective equipment Alcohol / drugs Distraction Fatigue/Drowsiness Surrogate Safety Measures (SSMs) Road Traffic Accidents Violations	Vehicle	Traffic volume Presence of warning signs Pre/post-crash care systems Speed Traffic management system C-ITS	Road condition Objects, clear zones and road restraint systems Intersections Vulnerable road users' facilities Maintenance / road works Speed management

The SCC framework is structured into four top-level categories, road users, vehicles, traffic management and communication, and road infrastructure while following a clear hierarchy, from safety criterion to KPI, as presented in Table 3-1. Each entry specifies an operational definition, the exposure or denominator (for example, number or proportion of observed vehicles or road users), minimum sample sizes and observation windows, and recommended data sources, so measurements are comparable across use cases. For each proposed KPI a relevance to the ISAD levels

is provided, represented from A (Cooperative Driving) to E (Conventional Infrastructure/Non AV Support).

The SCC will be utilized by the iDriving use cases, within which the data will be collected and quantified as KPI according to the SCC. Protocols, and governance, validation and update procedures are defined in the iDriving project documentation. The road networks which are part of Use Cases, will be assessed and categorised based on the services and information they provide, including readiness for CAV based on the ISAD levels. The heat map will show a visual representation of KPIs and network quality in a specific geographic area.

4 Concept of the Enhanced SCC

4.1 Framework and Categories explanation

The SCC Framework presents an integrated bottom-up and top-down approach to assessing road safety and infrastructure performance. It establishes clear connections between high-level safety objectives, operational monitoring tools, measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and the resulting impacts, as presented in Figure 4-1.

Figure 4-1 iDriving approach with SCC framework presenting the bottom-up and top-down approach, linking the monitoring tools, SCC KPIs and final impacts assessment

At the top level, the framework begins with the Safety Criteria Catalogue, which organizes safety objectives into four main domains: road users, vehicles, traffic management and communication, and infrastructure. These domains reflect transportation system components and guide the definition of the expected impacts, such as greater voluntary adherence to speed limits, fewer accidents, reduced maintenance-related traffic delays, and improved detection of infrastructure defects like cracks and potholes. This top-down perspective ensures that safety goals are consistently linked to tangible impacts on the transport system.

From the bottom-up perspective, the framework incorporates practical monitoring tools and measures that directly collect data and influence system performance. These include speed monitoring systems, in-vehicle notifications, variable message signs (VMS) in work zones, and cameras equipped with artificial intelligence for defect recognition. Each tool generates KPIs, such as the number of users exceeding the speed limit, the number of drivers informed, or the number of potholes detected. These KPIs provide quantifiable evidence of system performance and serve as the operational foundation for impact assessment.

The central role of KPIs is to act as the link between tools and impacts. They translate raw monitoring data into performance measures that can be systematically assessed against the safety criteria. For example, monitoring speeding violations informs the level of voluntary speed adherence, while pothole detection figures inform infrastructure safety improvements.

By combining the top-down definition of safety priorities with the bottom-up evidence from monitoring tools and KPIs, the SCC Framework creates a feedback loop that supports both strategic decision-making and operational improvements. This integrated approach ensures that safety impacts are not only targeted at the policy level but are also grounded in real-world, measurable outcomes.

4.2 Relevance for iDriving

Six distinct scenarios are defined for the comprehensive evaluation of iDriving's technological capabilities. These scenarios are implemented across six unique pilot sites, each situated in a different country and different conditions. They are organized into three use cases, with each use case comprising two scenarios that share similar objectives and motivations. The countries selected for these trials are Austria, France, Spain, Croatia, Romania, and Greece, as shown in Table 4-1.

SCC KPIs will quantify road safety impacts based on the technical solutions implemented in real-world scenarios and relevant environments, which will be used to validate their effectiveness as per end-user and stakeholder feedback. Each pilot will adhere to ethical and legal standards, including data protection and obtaining necessary approvals.

Table 4-1 Overview of iDriving Use Cases, expected impacts and relevant SCC KPI category

Objectives	UC location	Expected impacts	Examples of SCC KPI
Enhanced Logging and User Interaction Monitoring for Improvement of Road Infrastructure	UC1.1 Graz (Austria)	↑30% helmet and seatbelt usage; ↓20% in minor and major collisions; ↓15% traffic congestion during peak hours; identify and rectify 50% high-risk zones	Road users, Traffic management and communication
	UC1.2 Nevers (France)	↑ 30% helmet and seatbelt usage; ↓ 20% in road incidents; ↓15% traffic congestion during peak hours; identify and rectify 50% high-risk zones	Road users, Traffic management and communication
Infrastructure Maintenance and Road Monitoring for Hazards	UC2.1 Karlovac (Croatia)	Inform 70% road users about maintenance in real-time; ↓25% traffic delays; ↓30% congestion in high-risk areas via route suggestions; ↓ work zone incidents; detect 80%+ major road defects	Road users, Traffic management and communication, Infrastructure
	UC2.2 Thessaloniki (Greece)	↑30% voluntary safety rule adherence (helmet and seatbelt usage); ↑60% speed of construction detection and reporting; ↓30% congestion in high-risk areas via route suggestions; ↓30% weather related incidents	Road users, Traffic management and communication, Infrastructure
Real-Time Incident Prediction, Detection and Response	UC3.1 Alba Iulia (Romania)	↓30% alcohol related accidents; ↓30% accidents from risky overtakes at blind bends; ↓50% time to detect incidents or accidents; ↓40% incidents in high-risk zones via heatmaps; Inform 70% road users about maintenance in real-time; identify and improve 50% high risk zones; ↓30% emergency response times	Road users, Traffic management and communication
	UC3.2 (Spain)	↓30% alcohol related accidents, ↓30% accidents from risky overtakes at blind bends; identify and improve 50% high risk zones; ↓50% time to detect incidents or accidents; Inform 70% road users about maintenance in real-time; ↓30% emergency response times	Road users, Traffic management and communication

5 SCC categories and definition of Key Performance Indicators

The Key Performance Indicator Card template is presented in Figure 5-1, structured tool for defining and documenting safety metrics within Safety Criteria Catalogue. It starts with a unique code and description. Following, it outlines performance goal, calculation details (frequency, unit, and formula) along with relevant standards. It also requires identifying all data sources, necessary minimal data for calculation, input tools and data limitations. Finally, it has clear designation of responsibility, notes the relevant use case, target areas and leaves space for comments on future improvement plans. For SCC category that is relevant for the assessment of road system readiness for CAVs, the ISAD level categorization should be assessed during the KPI determination. If the category has no relevance for ISAD (e.g. road users and vehicles), “not applicable” category has been assigned.

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: Title	
KPI Code: SCC_GROUPX_X	Description: Short description of the KPI.	
Calculation frequency: Frequency of the data collection/ calculation	Unit: Unit of measure	
Relevant standard: Standards and literature sources relevant for the KPI.		
Calculation Formula: <i>Formula or other way of quantification</i>		
Data and Information Sources: Any information sources relevant for the KPI, e.g. stationary camera, predictive monitoring, baseline assessments...		
Preferred direction: ↑ or ↓	Target users: e.g. road users, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 5-1 KPI card template

5.1 Road users

The Users (SCC_U) category is dedicated to measuring and evaluating behaviour, compliance to traffic laws and overall safety profile of road users in different vehicle types. It is based on 8 KPIs derived from BASELINE Project (2020-2022) which are therefore covered in first 5 subcategories. They are: Speed limit compliance (U1_X), Safety belt (U2-X), Protective Equipment (U3_X), Alcohol / drug usage (U4_X) & Distraction (U5_X). New introduced categories measure road user Fatigue / Drowsiness (U6_X) to capture the behaviour of drivers impacted by tiredness. Surrogate Safety Measures (SSMs) (U7_X) are designed to measure current and predicted safety performance to provide dynamic assessment of risk. Subcategory Road Traffic Accidents (U8_X) measures fatalities and injuries. Final subcategory, Violations (U9_X) monitors compliance of road users in regard to traffic light and lane usage violations. The data for these metrics will primarily be captured using stationary cameras and predictive monitoring tools that analyse traffic flow and identify non-compliant behaviour.

The overview of all KPIs for Road Users category are presented in Table 5-1. In the next paragraphs the KPI card for each criteria is provided.

Table 5-1 Overview of SCC KPIs for Road Users category

Group	Criteria	Code	KPI
U1	Speed limit compliance	U1_1	Speed limit compliance
		U1_2	Operating speed (85th percentile)
U2	Safety belt	U2_1	Safety belt usage
		U2_2	Child restraint system usage
U3	Protective equipment	U3_1	Protective equipment usage
U4	Alcohol / drugs	U4_1	Alcohol usage
		U4_2	Drug usage
U5	Distraction	U5_1	Handheld mobile device distraction
U6	Fatigue/Drowsiness	U6_1	User Fatigue/Drowsiness
U7	Surrogate Safety Measures (SSMs)	U7_1	Time To Collision (TTC)
		U7_2	Time Headway (THW)
		U7_3	Post Encroachment Time (PET)
U8	Road Traffic Accidents	U8_1	Fatalities and accidents
U9	Violations	U9_1	Traffic Light signal violation by road users
		U9_2	Lane usage violations

5.1.1 Speed limit compliance

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Speed limit compliance</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_U1_1	Description: % of vehicles traveling within the speed limit by vehicle types.	
Calculation frequency: For selected location in the free-flow traffic		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: Van den Broek B., Aarts, L. & Silverans, P. (2023). Baseline report on the KPI Speeding. Baseline project, Brussels: Vias institute		
Calculation Formula: $SLC_{vtype} = \frac{N_{compliant,vtype}}{N_{total,vtype}} \times 100$ <p>Where:</p> <p>$N_{compliant,vtype}$ is the total number of compliant vehicles of $vtype$</p> <p>$N_{total,vtype}$ is the total number of vehicles of $vtype$</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stationary camera able to capture vehicle speed ▪ National reports ▪ Sample size: Min 2000 observations, Min 500 observations / road type (rural, urban, motorway), Min 10 locations / road type, the proportion of observations at each of the three road types should be at least 20% 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Road users / drivers of motorized vehicles, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Operating speed (85th percentile)</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_U1_2	Description: The speed below which 85% of vehicles are driving.	
Calculation frequency: For selected location in the free-flow traffic		Unit: km/h
Relevant standard / literature: Van den Broek B., Aarts, L. & Silverans, P. (2023). Baseline report on the KPI Speeding. Baseline project, Brussels: Vias institute		
Calculation Formula: $V_{85} = P_{85}(v)$ <p>Where:</p> <p>P_{85} value below which 85% of the observed speeds</p> <p>v is observed individual vehicle speeds</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stationary camera able to capture vehicle speed ▪ National reports ▪ Sample size: Min 2000 observations, Min 500 observations / road type (rural, urban, motorway), Min 10 locations / road type, the proportion of observations at each of the three road types should be at least 20% 		
Preferred direction: n/a	Target users: Road users / drivers of motorized vehicles	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.1.2 Safety belt usage

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Safety belt Usage</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_U2_1	Description: % of vehicle occupants using the safety belt.	
Calculation frequency: For selected location in the free-flow traffic		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: Van den Broek B., Aarts, L. & Silverans, P. (2022). Baseline report on the KPI Safety belt and Child restraint systems. Baseline project, Brussels: Vias institute		
Calculation Formula: $SBU = \frac{N_{belted}}{N_{total}} \times 100\%$ <p>Where:</p> <p>N_{belted} is the number of belted occupants</p> <p>N_{total} is the total occupants</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Statistical data (Police) ▪ Stationary camera able to capture seatbelt usage 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Road users in motorized vehicles, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Child Restraint System Usage</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_U2_2	Description: % of vehicle occupants using child restraint system correctly.	
Calculation frequency: For selected location in the free-flow traffic		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: Van den Broek B., Aarts, L. & Silverans, P. (2022). Baseline report on the KPI Safety belt and Child restraint systems. Baseline project, Brussels: Vias institute		
Calculation Formula: $CRSU = \frac{N_{\text{Child Restraint System}}}{N_{\text{Children}}} \times 100\%$ <p>Where:</p> <p>$N_{\text{ChildRestrainSystem}}$ is the number of users using Child restraint system</p> <p>N_{Children} is the total children's occupants</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Statistical data (e.g. Police) ▪ Cameras ▪ Survey data 		
Preferred direction: <p style="text-align: center;">↑</p>	Target users: Children in motorized vehicles, drivers of motorized vehicles, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.1.3 Protective equipment

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Protective equipment Usage</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_U3_1	Description: % of road users of two wheelers wearing a protective helmet.	
Calculation frequency: For selected location (minimum traffic flow of at least 10 vehicles passing per hour is required)		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: Yannis, G., Folla K. (2022). Baseline report on the KPI Helmet use among Cyclists and Powered two-wheelers (PTWs). Baseline project, Brussels Vias institute		
Calculation Formula: $Helmet_{vtype} = \frac{N_{helmet,vtype}}{N_{total,vtype}} \times 100\%$ <p>Where:</p> <p>$N_{helmet,vtype}$ is the total number of vehicles wearing helmet of vtype</p> <p>$N_{total,vtype}$ is the total number of compliant vehicles of vtype</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Statistical data ▪ Police ▪ Stationary camera able to capture usage of helmets ▪ Sample size: Min 2.000 observations / category, Min 500 observations / category / road type, Min 10 locations / road type; and 10 locations / time period, at least 2 locations for each stratification combination, Driver / Passenger, • Age (if legally relevant) 		
Preferred direction: <p style="text-align: center;">↑</p>	Target: Users of 2-wheelers, bicycles, scooters and motorcycles, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.1.4 Alcohol / drugs

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Alcohol Usage</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_U4_1	Description: % of drivers driving within the legal limit for blood alcohol content (BAC).	
Calculation frequency: night/day and week/weekend		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: Yannis, G., Folla K. (2022). Baseline report on the KPI Driving under the Influence of Alcohol. Baseline project, Brussels: Vias institute		
Calculation Formula: $AU = 1 - \frac{N_{al}}{N_{total}} \times 100\%$ <p>Where:</p> <p>N_{al} is the total number of vehicles above alcohol legal limit</p> <p>$N_{total, vtype}$ is the total number of vehicles</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Statistical data ▪ Police (roadside measurements) ▪ Survey data 		
Preferred direction: <div style="text-align: center;">↓</div>	Target users: Drivers of motorized vehicles, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Drug Usage</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_U4_2	Description: % of drivers driving within the legal limit of drug usage.	
Calculation frequency: night/day and week/weekend		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: European Commission (2023). Safety Performance Indicator report – Alcohol and drugs. European Road Safety Observatory. Brussels, European Commission, Directorate General for Transport		
Calculation Formula: $DU = 1 - \frac{N_{dr}}{N_{total}} \times 100\%$ <p>Where:</p> <p>N_{dr} is the total number of vehicles above drug legal limit</p> <p>$N_{total, vtype}$ is the total number of vehicles</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Police (roadside measurements) ▪ Statistical data ▪ Survey data 		
Preferred direction: <div style="text-align: center;">↓</div>	Target users: Drivers of motorized vehicles, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.1.5 Distraction

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Handheld Mobile device Distraction</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_U5_1	Description: % of drivers NOT using handheld mobile device.	
Calculation frequency: night/day and week/weekend		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: Boets, S. (2023). Baseline report on the KPI Distraction. Baseline project, Brussels: Vias institute		
Calculation Formula: $MDis = 1 - \frac{N_{distracted}}{N_{total}} \times 100\%$ <p>Where:</p> <p><i>MDis</i> – % of drivers not using handheld mobiles</p> <p>$N_{distracted}$ is the total number of drivers using mobile while driving</p> <p>N_{total} is the total number of vehicles</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stationary camera ▪ Statistical data ▪ Police ▪ Survey data 		
Preferred direction: ↓	Target users: Drivers of motorized vehicles, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.1.6 Fatigue/Drowsiness

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">User Fatigue/Drowsiness</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_U6_1	Description: % of drivers driving when they are sleepy.	
Calculation frequency: night/day and week/weekend		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: European Commission (2023). Safety Performance Indicator report – Fatigue. European Road Safety Observatory. Brussels, European Commission, Directorate General for Transport		
Calculation Formula: $Fatigue = \frac{N_{fatigue}}{N_{total}} \times 100\%$ <p>Where</p> <p>$N_{fatigue}$ is the total number of drivers presenting fatigue/drowsiness symptoms</p> <p>N_{total} is the total number of vehicles</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Statistical data ▪ Police ▪ Survey data 		
Preferred direction: <div style="text-align: center;">↓</div>	Target users: Drivers of motorized vehicles, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.1.7 Surrogate Safety Measures (SSMs)

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Time To Collision</h2>										
KPI Code: SCC_U7_1	Description: Estimation of the time remaining until two vehicles would collide if their current paths remained unchanged.										
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: sec									
Relevant standard / literature: Hayward, J.Ch. (1972). Near miss determination through use of a scale of danger. Report no. TTSC 7115, The Pennsylvania State University, Pennsylvania.											
Calculation Formula: $TTC = \frac{D}{V_f - V_l}$ <p>Where:</p> <p>D is distance between the front of the follower and the rear of the leader (meters)</p> <p>V_f and V_l the respective speeds (m/s) of the follower and leader vehicle</p> Criteria for the TTC evaluation: <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1352 1305 1525"> <tr> <td><1.5</td> <td>Critical / Near-collision</td> <td>Immediate evasive action required</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.5-3.0</td> <td>Warning</td> <td>High-risk following or potential hazard</td> </tr> <tr> <td>>3.0</td> <td>Safe</td> <td>Normal car-following</td> </tr> </table>			<1.5	Critical / Near-collision	Immediate evasive action required	1.5-3.0	Warning	High-risk following or potential hazard	>3.0	Safe	Normal car-following
<1.5	Critical / Near-collision	Immediate evasive action required									
1.5-3.0	Warning	High-risk following or potential hazard									
>3.0	Safe	Normal car-following									
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crash database (from the police and / or from the municipality) Operational data (traffic volume, vehicle classification) 											
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Traffic managers, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>									

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Time Headway (THW)</h2>										
KPI Code: SCC_U7_2	Description: Time gap between two vehicles passing the same point.										
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: sec									
Relevant standard / literature: Vogel, K. (2003). A comparison of headway and time to collision as safety indicators. Accident Analysis & Prevention, 35(3), 427–433. doi:10.1016/S0001-4575(02)00022-2											
Calculation Formula: $THW = \frac{D}{V_f}$ <p>Where:</p> <p>D is distance between the front of the follower and the rear of the leader (meters)</p> <p>V_f is the speed (m/s) of the follower vehicle</p> Criteria for the THW evaluation: <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1317 1120 1496"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Critical</td> <td>Unsafe following distance</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1-1.5</td> <td>Moderate risk</td> <td>Aggressive or short headway</td> </tr> <tr> <td>>1.5</td> <td>Safe</td> <td>Normal driving distance</td> </tr> </table>			1	Critical	Unsafe following distance	1-1.5	Moderate risk	Aggressive or short headway	>1.5	Safe	Normal driving distance
1	Critical	Unsafe following distance									
1-1.5	Moderate risk	Aggressive or short headway									
>1.5	Safe	Normal driving distance									
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CCTV providing video footage (object detection and tracking) • Sensor data with timestamps 											
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Traffic managers, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>									

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Post Encroachment Time (PET)</h2>													
KPI Code: SCC_U7_3	Description: The time interval between the moment the first road user deviates from the path of the second road user and the moment the second road user crosses the path of the first road user													
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: sec												
Relevant standard / literature:: Gettman, D. & Head, L. (2003) Surrogate Safety Measures From Traffic Simulation Models, Final Report, Publication No: FHWA-RD-03-050.														
Calculation Formula: $PET = t_{leave} - t_{reach}$ <p>Where:</p> <p>t_{leave} is the time when the first vehicle leaves the potential conflict area</p> <p>t_{reach} is the time when the second vehicle enters the same area</p> <p>Criteria for the PET evaluation:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="213 1397 1142 1619"> <tr> <td></td> <td>Critical</td> <td>Very near-miss, collision likely</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.0 – 1.5</td> <td>High risk</td> <td>Serious conflict</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.5 – 2.25</td> <td>Moderate risk</td> <td>Close but acceptable</td> </tr> <tr> <td>>2.25</td> <td>Safe</td> <td>Low conflict likelihood</td> </tr> </table>				Critical	Very near-miss, collision likely	1.0 – 1.5	High risk	Serious conflict	1.5 – 2.25	Moderate risk	Close but acceptable	>2.25	Safe	Low conflict likelihood
	Critical	Very near-miss, collision likely												
1.0 – 1.5	High risk	Serious conflict												
1.5 – 2.25	Moderate risk	Close but acceptable												
>2.25	Safe	Low conflict likelihood												
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CCTV providing video footage (object detection and tracking) • Vehicle trajectory logs (e.g., GPS or sensor streams) 														
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Road users, traffic managers, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>												

5.1.8 Road Traffic Accidents

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Fatalities and Accidents</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_U8_1	Description: Accidents, fatalities (any person killed immediately or dying within 30 days as a result of an injury accident, excluding suicides) and injured persons by location, time of occurrence and road conditions and by gender and age group.	
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: World Health Organization (WHO) (2025) Definition of a road traffic death by WHO and the health sector.		
Calculation Formula: $ACC_{Rtype} = \frac{\sum event_{gender,age,type,location}}{veh} \times 100$ <p>Where:</p> <p><i>event</i> is at a current location (road, intersection) for a <i>type</i> of event (accidents, fatalities) of people of precises <i>gender</i> and <i>age</i></p> <p><i>Veh</i> is the total number of vehicles per day</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ National traffic statistics ▪ Local statistical data (e.g. Local police) 		
Preferred direction: <div style="text-align: center;">↓</div>	Target users: Policy makers, traffic managers, police, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.1.9 Violations

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Traffic Light Signal Violation</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_U9_1	Description: % of road users violating the traffic light signal by vehicle types.	
Calculation frequency: <i>For selected time period</i>		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: National rules and regulations of traffic		
Calculation Formula: $TLS_{violation} = \frac{N_{violations,vtype}}{N_{total,vtype}} \times 100\%$ <p>Where:</p> <p>$N_{violations,vtype}$ is the total number of violations for each road user type</p> <p>$N_{total,vtype}$ is the total number of road users of certain type</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stationary camera ▪ Police ▪ Statistical data on road accidents data ▪ Survey data 		
Preferred direction: <div style="text-align: center;">↓</div>	Target users: Policy makers, police, traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Lane Usage Violations</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_U9_2	Description: % of road users not using the correct lane by vehicle types.	
Calculation frequency: <i>For selected time period</i>		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: National rules and regulations of traffic		
Calculation Formula: $Lane_{violation} = \frac{N_{violations,vtype}}{N_{total,vtype}} \times 100\%$ <p>Where:</p> <p>$N_{violations,vtype}$ is the total number of violations for each road user type</p> <p>$N_{total,vtype}$ is the total number of road users of certain type</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stationary camera ▪ Police ▪ Statistical data on road accidents data ▪ Survey data 		
Preferred direction: <div style="text-align: center;">↓</div>	Target users: Policy makers, police, traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.2 Vehicles

The Vehicles (SCC_V) category is concerned with evaluating the inherent safety of vehicles. It takes into account their passive and active features, crashworthiness and overall composition of the fleet operating on road network. It consists of 3 KPIs, EuroNCAP score (V1_1) which rates cars on a five star scale based on their safety in the events of a crash. Average age of vehicles (V1_2) measures the average age of fleet in the road network, which suggests what level of safety features do the vehicles possess. Type of vehicle (V1_3) categorizes vehicles based on the type of license required to operate them. Main source for this category is the Euro NCAP 5 star categorization which is continuously updated as new safety features become available for vehicles. Finally, Autonomy rating (V1_4) defines the vehicle level of automation in driving operations.

Data for this category will be primarily collected via National Registry Databases.

The overview of all KPIs for Vehicles category are presented in Table 5-2. In the next paragraphs the KPI card for each criteria is provided.

Table 5-2 Overview of SCC KPIs for Vehicles category

Group	Criteria	Code	KPI
V1	Vehicle	V1_1	EuroNCAP
		V1_2	Average age of vehicles
		V1_3	Type of vehicle
		V1_4	Autonomy Rating

5.2.1 Vehicle

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">EuroNCAP</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_VI_1	Description: <p>Five-star safety rating determined from a series of vehicle tests, designed and carried out by NCAP.</p>	
Calculation frequency: <p style="text-align: center;">Annually</p>		Unit: <p style="text-align: center;">Stars (0-5)</p>
Relevant standard / literature: <p>EuroNCAP – The European New Car Assessment Programme https://www.euroncap.com/en</p>		
Calculation Formula: $mean(EuroNCAP_{type})$ <p>Where: EuroNCAP is rating of the <i>vehicle type</i> at the EuroNCAP test</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ National Vehicle Registration Database ▪ EuroNCAP Database ▪ Stationary camera videos or images 		
Preferred direction: <p style="text-align: center;">↑</p>	Target users: <p style="text-align: center;">Road users, traffic managers, car producers, policy makers</p>	ISAD Level <p style="text-align: center;">A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Average Age of Vehicle</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_VI_2	Description: Average age of vehicle in traffic.	
Calculation frequency: Annually		Unit: Years
Relevant standard / literature: ACEA, March 2024, Economic and Market Report, Global and EU auto industry: Full year 2023, https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/circularity/sectoral-modules/product-lifespans/evolution-of-the-average-passenger-car-age-in-the-eu-between-2013-and-2022		
Calculation Formula: $\text{mean}(\text{age}_{\text{type}})$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> age_{type} is age of the <i>vehicle type</i> 		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Vehicle Registration Database Stationary camera videos or images 		
Preferred direction: ↓	Target users: Policy makers, automobile manufacturers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Type of Vehicle</h2>											
KPI Code: SCC_V1_3	Description: Categorisation of vehicle depending on what type of license is needed to operate it.											
Calculation frequency: Annually		Unit: n/a										
Relevant standard / literature: European Commission (2007) Directive 2007/46/EC European Parliament (2013) Regulation (EU) No 168/2013												
Calculation Formula: $\frac{N_{type}}{N_{total}} \times 100$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ N_{type} is number of target type vehicles ▪ N_{total} is total number of observed vehicles 												
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ National Vehicle Registration Database ▪ EuroNCAP Database <p>Vehicle categories per license type:</p>												
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>License Category</th> <th>Notes</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>A, AM, A1, A2</td> <td>Motorcycles and mopeds</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B, BE</td> <td>Passenger cars and small trailers</td> </tr> <tr> <td>C, CE, C1, C1E</td> <td>Trucks and heavy goods vehicles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>D, DE, D1, D1E</td> <td>Buses and passenger transport vehicles</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		License Category	Notes	A, AM, A1, A2	Motorcycles and mopeds	B, BE	Passenger cars and small trailers	C, CE, C1, C1E	Trucks and heavy goods vehicles	D, DE, D1, D1E	Buses and passenger transport vehicles	
License Category	Notes											
A, AM, A1, A2	Motorcycles and mopeds											
B, BE	Passenger cars and small trailers											
C, CE, C1, C1E	Trucks and heavy goods vehicles											
D, DE, D1, D1E	Buses and passenger transport vehicles											
Preferred direction: n/a	Target users: Policy makers, automobile manufacturers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>										

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Autonomy Rating</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_V1_4	Description: Standardized 0-5 rating defining the level of automation in driving operations.	
Calculation frequency: Annually		Unit: Level (0-5)
Relevant standard / literature: SAE J3016_202104 Taxonomy and Definitions for Terms Related to Driving Automation Systems for On-Road Motor Vehicles (Revision APR2021)		
Calculation Formula: $SAE\ Level = Assigned\ level\ (0\ to\ 5)$ <p>Where</p> <p>Level 0: No Driving Automation</p> <p>Level 1: Driver Assistance</p> <p>Level 2: Partial Driving Automation</p> <p>Level 3: Conditional Driving Automation</p> <p>Level 4: High Driving Automation</p> <p>Level 5: Full Driving Automation</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Manufacturer technical specifications ▪ Vehicle Certification Documents 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Policy makers, traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.3 Traffic management and communication

Category Traffic Management and communication (SCC_TM) measures dynamic and characteristics of the traffic flow and the effectiveness of real-time communication systems. Metrics are organized in four subcategories. Traffic Volume (TM1_X) assess the quantity and composition of vehicle and vulnerable road user flow. Presence of warning signs (TM2_X) validates presence of warning signs and devices such as School Zone Warning, Weather Alerts System. Pre/post-crash care systems subcategory (TM3_X) is concerned with presence of systems that alert that can alert the road users about dangers or systems that allow road users to communicate with emergency teams. Speed (TM4_1) captures data on speed limit imposed on the road network. Traffic management system subcategory (TM5_X) collects data on presence and type of traffic lights and speed management measures. Finally, subcategory C-ITS (TM6_X) focuses on presence of advanced communication and cooperation systems that allow vehicles & infrastructure to exchange information. The overview of all SCC KPIs for TM category is presented in Table 5-3. In the next paragraphs the KPI card for each criteria is provided.

Table 5-3 Overview of SCC KPIs for Traffic management and communication category

Group	Criteria	Code	KPI
TM1	Traffic volume	TM1_1	Traffic Volume
		TM1_2	Intersection Traffic Volume
		TM1_3	Vulnerable Users Traffic Volume
		TM1_4	Land Use Traffic Flow Impact
TM2	Presence of warning signs	TM2_1	ITS Devices Penetration Ratio
		TM2_2	School zone Warning Penetration ratio
		TM2_3	Warning alerts System Penetration ratio
		TM2_4	Weather Alerts System Penetration ratio
		TM2_5	Driving Conditions
TM3	Post-crash care systems	TM3_1	Post-crash care
		TM3_2	Post-crash care investigation coverage
		TM3_3	Time to definitive care
		TM3_4	Recovery time
		TM3_5	Emergency Communication Effectiveness
		TM3_6	Use of advanced technologies in post-crash care
		TM3_7	Automatic Incident Detection
TM4	Speed	TM4_1	Speed limit
TM5	Traffic management system	TM5_1	Network Operational Centre (NOC)
		TM5_2	Traffic lights
		TM5_3	Speed management Measure (SMM)
TM6	C-ITS	TM6_1	In-vehicle communication system
		TM6_2	Mobile communication system
		TM6_3	V2V
		TM6_4	V2I
		TM6_5	I2I

5.3.1 Traffic volume

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Traffic Volume</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM1_1	Description: Measure the proportion of total traffic volume represented by a specific vehicle category to assess network usage composition.	
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: European Commission (2022) Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/670 of 2 February 2022 supplementing Directive 2010/40/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to the provision of EU-wide real-time traffic information services (Text with EEA relevance)		
Calculation Formula: $Traffic = \frac{N_{v,type}}{N_{total}} \times 100$ <p>Where:</p> <p>$N_{v,type}$ is number of road users of the vehicle type for the defined period</p> <p>N_{total} is number of all road users for the defined period</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stationary camera videos or images ▪ Local statistics from the municipality and / or police ▪ National database 		
Preferred direction: n/a	Target users: Road users, traffic managers, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Intersection Traffic Volume</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM1_2	Description: Measure the average traffic volume in the intersection observing the type of road user (pedestrian, car, motorcycle, etc.) and their direction.	
Calculation frequency: For selected location and period		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: European Commission (2022) Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/670 of 2 February 2022 supplementing Directive 2010/40/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to the provision of EU-wide real-time traffic information services (Text with EEA relevance)		
Calculation Formula: $N_{type,direction}$ <p>Where:</p> $N_{type,direction} = \text{Volume of traffic per type and per direction}$		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic counters • CCTV providing video footage 		
Preferred direction: n/a	Target users: Road users, traffic managers, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Vulnerable Users Traffic Volume</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM1_3	Description: Determine the share of vulnerable road users (pedestrians, 2-wheelers, wheelchair users and other non-motorized users) in total traffic volume to assess exposure.	
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: European Commission (2024) Facts and Figures Serious injuries. European Road Safety Observatory. Brussels, European Commission, Directorate General for Transport.		
Calculation Formula: $Traffic_{vul} = \frac{N_{vul,type}}{N_{vul,total}} \times 100$ <p>Where:</p> <p>$N_{vul,type}$ is number of vulnerable road users of specific type (pedestrians or cyclists) for the selected period</p> <p>$N_{vul,total}$ is number of all vulnerable road users for the selected period</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stationary camera providing videos or images ▪ Police ▪ Survey data 		
Preferred direction: n/a	Target users: Pedestrians, 2-wheelers, wheelchair users and other non-motorized users, traffic managers, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Land Use Traffic Flow Impact</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM1_4	Description: Determine the overall traffic flow impacted by or attributable to various surrounding land uses (e.g., residential, commercial, industrial).	
Calculation frequency: For selected territory		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: Rupprecht Consult (2019), Guidelines for Developing and Implementing a Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan, Second Edition, 2019		
Calculation Formula: $Q_i = \sum_0^n V_{vtype} \beta_n$ <p>Where:</p> <p>β_n is land use weight coefficient showing how strongly a land use contribute to the total flow at location i</p> <p>The total traffic flow at location i be Q_i is split into n sub flows (e.g., by land use β_n).</p> <p>The goal is for each land-use across the road to get the impact on the flows for each road type user.</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stationary camera videos or images ▪ Maps ▪ Local statistics from the municipality and / or police 		
Preferred direction: n/a	Target users: Urban planners, traffic managers, police, policy makers, road users,	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.3.2 Presence of warning signs

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">ITS Devices Penetration Ratio</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM2_1	Description: Presence of ITS devices: queue alerts, variable message signs.	
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: NAPCORE (National Access Point Coordination Organisation for Europe https://napcore.eu/description-naps/) ITS Directive 2010/40/EU, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32010L0040 Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/670 – EU-wide real-time traffic information services (RTTI), https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022R0670 Delegated Regulation (EU) 2017/1926, DR 2024/490 – EU-wide multimodal travel information services (MMTIS), https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg.del/2024/490/oj		
Calculation Formula: $ITS \text{ Penetration ratio} = \frac{\sum(L_i \times ITS_i)}{\sum L_i} \times 100$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ $ITS_i = 1$ if segment i has an ITS device, otherwise = 0 ▪ L_i = Segment length (km) 		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ITS data ▪ National Access Point data ▪ Data from the municipality 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Road users, traffic managers, police, policy makers	ISAD Level The level should be determined in line with Table 2-1. A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">School zone Warning Penetration ratio</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM2_2	Description: Presence of school zone warning system within defined area and time period.	
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: ITS Directive 2010/40/EU, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32010L0040 Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/670 – EU-wide real-time traffic information services (RTTI), https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022R0670		
Calculation Formula: $SZW \text{ Penetration ratio} = \frac{\sum(L_i \times SZW_i)}{\sum L_i}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ $SZW_i = 1$ if segment i has a school zone warning, otherwise = 0 ▪ $L_i =$ Segment length (km) 		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Images or videos from the movable camera ▪ Data from the municipality and / or police 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Vulnerable road users, traffic managers, police, policy makers	ISAD Level The level should be determined in line with Table 2-1. A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Warning alerts System Penetration ratio</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM2_3	Description: Presence of warning alert system about road incidents within defined area and time period.	
Calculation frequency: For selected period		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: ITS Directive 2010/40/EU, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32010L0040 Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/670 – EU-wide real-time traffic information services (RTTI), https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022R0670		
Calculation Formula: $WAS \text{ Penetration ratio} = \frac{\sum(L_i \times WAS_i)}{\sum L_i}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ $WAS_i = 1$ if segment i has a warning alerts system, otherwise = 0 ▪ $L_i =$ Segment length (km) 		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Data from the traffic management dept. at municipality ▪ Images, videos from the stationary and movable cameras 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Road users, traffic managers, police, policy makers	ISAD Level The level should be determined in line with Table 2-1. A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Weather Alerts System Penetration ratio</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM2_4	Description: Presence of weather related warnings linked to real-time weather data and forecast data.	
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: ITS Directive 2010/40/EU, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32010L0040 Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/670 – EU-wide real-time traffic information services (RTTI), https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022R0670		
Calculation Formula: $WtAS \text{ Penetration ratio} = \frac{\sum(L_i \times WtAS_i)}{\sum L_i}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ $WtAS_i = 1$ if segment i has a warning alerts system, otherwise = 0 ▪ $L_i =$ Segment length (km) 		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Road Weather Information Systems (RWIS) - Meteorological stations - Data from the traffic management dept. at municipality 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Road users, traffic managers / operators	ISAD Level The level should be determined in line with Table 2-1. A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Driving Conditions</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM2_5	Description: Mechanisms to inform road users about driving conditions in order to prevent accidents or incidents.	
Calculation frequency: For the selected territory and period (part of the day, usually linked to the weather forecast)	Unit: Descriptive (dry, wet, flooded, ice, snow, slush, fog, wind, heat, sun glare, ...)	
Relevant standard / literature: US FHWA Road Weather Management System Wiener, G., Petzke, W., Brummet, T., & Walker, C. (2023). Automated Extraction of Weather Variables from Imagery, Technical Report. Aurora program FHWA.		
Calculation Formula: Linked to the weather real time data and weather forecast Thresholds linked to local situation (e.g. road in the valley – wet, low visibility due to the fog, etc.) established based on the historical data.		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meteorological stations - Cameras (fixed and movable) - Environmental Sensor Stations (ESS) - Road Weather Information Systems (RWIS) 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Road users, traffic managers / operators	ISAD Level The level should be determined in line with Table 2-1. A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/>

5.3.3 Post-crash care systems

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Post-crash care</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM3_1	Description: Time elapsed between the emergency call following a collision and the arrival of the emergency services at the scene.	
Calculation frequency: Annual per territory		Unit: Minutes, seconds
Relevant standard / literature: Baseline (2021). Methodological guidelines for KPI Post-crash Care, Baseline. European Transport Safety Council (ETSC) (2021). Reducing road deaths among young people aged 15 to 30. PIN Flash Report 41.		
Calculation Formula: $PCC = T_{EMSS} - T_{eCall}$ <p> <i>PCC</i> – Post Crash Care <i>T_{EMSS}</i>- timestamp when EMS unit arrived at the crash scene <i>T_{eCall}</i> - timestamp when the emergency call is taken by the dispatching centre <i>EMS</i> – Emergency Medical Services </p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data from dispatching centre (112) – time stamps for receipt of the call and arrival of the emergency unit at the road crash scene - Link to Road Traffic Accidents data (SCC.U.8.1) - The minimum requirement is to provide the 95th percentile of the time elapsed between the emergency call and the arrival of the emergency services at the crash scene for the selected territory. 		
Preferred direction: ↓	Target users: EMS, police, policy makers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Post-crash care investigation coverage</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM3_2	Description: The percentage of crashes subjected to thorough post-crash investigations to identify contributing factors and improve future response, ensuring that the underlying causes of crashes are understood and addressed to prevent recurrence	
Calculation frequency: Annual per territory		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: Baseline (2021). Methodological guidelines for KPI Post-crash Care, Baseline. European Commission (2021). EU Road Safety Policy Framework 2021-2030. EvoRoads (2025) D1-1 Best practices and baseline catalogue of safety criteria		
Calculation Formula: The analysis could take into account following parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Location of crash, road type (urban, rural, motorway) - Crash severity (number of casualties, number of fatalities at the location, number o fatalities at hospital) - Type of emergency services - % of serious injury crashes where no emergency care were provided - % of road traffic crashes resulting in serious injury where the response time did not exceed the national target - Distribution of EMS units - Etc. 		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital data stored in event data recorders - Reports - Link to Road Traffic Accidents data (SCC.U.8.1) and Post Crash Care (SCC.TMM.3.1) 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: EMS, police, policy makers, traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Time to definitive care</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM3_3	Description: Time from the crash event to when the victim receives definitive medical care (e.g., hospital admission).	
Calculation frequency: Annual per territory		Unit: Minutes, seconds
Relevant standard / literature: NHTSA (2019). Traffic Safety Facts.		
Calculation Formula: $TTDC = T_{hosp} - T_{eCall}$ <i>TTDC</i> – time to definitive care <i>T_{hosp}</i> – timestamp of arrival to the hospital <i>T_{eCall}</i> - timestamp when the emergency call is taken by the dispatching centre		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data from dispatching centre (112) and from hospital / medical care – time stamps for receipt of the call and arrival of the victims to the hospital - Link to Road Traffic Accidents data (SCC.U.8.1) and Post Crash Care (SCC.TMM.3.1) 		
Preferred direction: ↓	Target users: EMS, police, policy makers, traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Recovery time</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM3_4	Description: Time elapsed between incident detection and full traffic recovery.	
Calculation frequency: Annual per territory		Unit: Hours, Minutes, seconds
Relevant standard / literature: EvoRoads (2025) D1-1 Best practices and baseline catalogue of safety criteria		
Calculation Formula: $RCT = T_{FTR} - T_{eCall}$ <p> <i>RCT</i> – time required for full traffic recovery <i>T_{FTR}</i> – timestamp of full traffic recovery <i>T_{eCall}</i> - timestamp when the emergency call is taken by the dispatching centre </p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data from dispatching centre (112) - Data can come from traffic incident reports, real-time monitoring systems, ITS. - Link to Road Traffic Accidents data (SCC.U.8.1), Post Crash Care (SCC.TMM.3.1) 		
Preferred direction: <div style="text-align: center;">↓</div>	Target users: EMS, police, policy makers, traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Emergency Communication Effectiveness</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM3_5	Description: Measures the usage rate and effectiveness of emergency communication systems (e.g., eCall) in crash response.	
Calculation frequency: Annually per territory		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: European Emergency Number Association (EENA) (2016). eCall Key Performance Indicators.		
Calculation Formula: $Emergency\ Comm = \frac{\sum(eCalls_{road\ crash\ i})}{\sum road\ crash\ response_i} \times 100\%$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - $eCalls_{road\ crash\ i}$ - number of advanced eCalls activated in road crash incidents per year - $road\ crash\ response_i$ - total number of road crash incident responses per year 		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data from dispatching centre (112) - Police records on road crashes responses - Link to SCC.U.8.1, SCC.TM.3.1, SCC.TM.3.2, SCC.TM.3.3 		
<p>The diagram illustrates the eCall architecture. A car on the left sends data to a satellite (GNSS POSITIONING) and a base station (MSD). The satellite provides precise location data to the car. The base station transmits this data to a 112 emergency call center. The 112 center operator uses the location data on a map and communicates with the car. The car also sends data to a VMS (Variable Message Sign) and a traffic information system. The traffic information system sends data to a traffic info system. The traffic info system sends data to an integrated emergency system, which sends data to a rescue intervention system.</p>		
eCall architecture (EENA, 2016)		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: EMS, police, policy makers, traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Use of advanced technologies in post-crash care</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM3_6	Description: Portion of the advanced technologies implementation in post-crash care, e.g. telemedicine and drone delivery of medical supplies such as first aid kits and AEDs in post-crash scenarios, particularly in remote (rural) or congested areas.	
Calculation frequency: Annual per territory		Unit: %
Relevant standard / literature: Pulsiri, N., & Vatananan-Thesenvitz, R. (2021). Drones in Emergency Medical Services: A Systematic Literature Review with Bibliometric Analysis. International Journal of Innovation and Technology Management, 18(04), 2097001. https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219877020970019 . EvoRoads (2025) D1-1 Best practices and baseline catalogue of safety criteria		
Calculation Formula: $AdvTech_{PCC} = \frac{\sum(AdvTech_{PCC\ i})}{\sum road\ crash\ response_i} \times 100\%$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - $AdvTech_{PCC\ i}$ - number of advanced technologies used in post-crash care in road incidents per year - $road\ crash\ response_i$ - total number of road crash incident responses per year 		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data from dispatching centre (112) and police - Link to SCC.U.8.1, SCC.TM.3.1, SCC.TM.3.2, SCC.TM.3.3 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: EMS, police, policy makers, traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Automatic Incident Detection</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM3_7	Description: AID (automatic incident detection) systems detect accidents or unusual traffic patterns automatically and alert authorities.	
Calculation frequency: Per selected territory and time period.		Unit: /
Relevant standard / literature: EvoRoads (2025) D1-1 Best practices and baseline catalogue of safety criteria Wallace, et al. (2007/2009). Timeline for a Typical Traffic Incident.		
Calculation Formula: $AID \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if available} \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$ AID - automatic incident detection system		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensors (LiDar, thermal sensor) - CCTV Cameras - C-ITS 		
Preferred direction: n/a	Target users: traffic managers, road users, EMS, police,	ISAD Level The level should be determined in line with Table 2-1. A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/>

5.3.4 Speed

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Speed Limit</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM4_1	Description: Defined speed limit per road type and per location .	
Calculation frequency: Annually		Unit: Integer
Relevant standard / literature: National laws for Road Safety set speed limits		
Calculation Formula: $\text{Speed Limit}_{road,type}$ <p>Note:</p> <p>For motorways - the general speed limit in EU Member States is mostly 120 or 130 km/h. Germany does not have a general speed limit for motorways, but a recommended speed of 130 km/h.</p> <p>For rural roads - the general speed limit in EU MS is mostly 80 or 90 km/h</p> <p>For urban roads - the general speed limit in EU MS is mostly 50 km/h.</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Law for Road Safety • Traffic operator / manager 		
Preferred direction: n/a	Target users: Road users, police, policy makers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/>

5.3.5 Traffic management system

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Network Operational Centre (NOC)</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM5_1	Description: Existence of Network Operational Centre at the Traffic Operator Unit. Sometimes called also Traffic Control centre.	
Calculation frequency: For the selected territory and period.		Unit: Binary
Relevant standard / literature: EC (2016) COM (2016) 766 - A European strategy on Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems, a milestone towards cooperative, connected and automated mobility		
Calculation Formula: $NOC \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if available} \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$ <p>NOC – Network Operational Centre</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fixed and movable cameras - Roadside sensors (traffic data – speed, volume, congestion) - Weather data (RWIS) - Automated vehicle location - Emergency calls, etc. 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Traffic managers, EMS, police, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Traffic Lights</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM5_2	Description: Presence and type of traffic lights (Static, dynamic) per road type.	
Calculation frequency: Fixed data in the system, updated when there is a change		Unit: Number and type
Relevant standard / literature: ISO 16508:1999 Road traffic lights — Photometric properties of 200 mm roundel signals		
Calculation Formula: $\textit{Traffic light}_{road,type}$ <p>- Number and type of Traffic lights per road section (location, type)</p>		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traffic operator / manager 		
Preferred direction:	Target users: Traffic manager, traffic planner / modeller, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Speed Management Measure (SMM)</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM5_2	Description: Presence of traffic calming measures (e.g. speed bumps).	
Calculation frequency: Annually		Unit: Number and type
Relevant standard / literature: Global Road Safety Partnership (2008). Speed management: a road safety manual for decision-makers and practitioners. Geneva, Switzerland: Global Road Safety Partnership		
Calculation Formula: $SMM_{road,type}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number and type of SMMs per road section (location, type) 		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic operator / manager • Images from movable cameras <div style="text-align: right;"> </div>		
Preferred direction: n/a	Target users: Vulnerable road users, drivers, traffic managers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.3.6 C-ITS

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">In-vehicle Communication System</h2>																						
KPI Code: SCC_TM6_1	Description: Average level of maturity of the In-Vehicle Communication System (IVCS) based on the capability to process and display information about surrounding environment. Ranging from legacy broadcast to cooperative safety alerts.																						
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: Integer 0 - 5																					
Relevant standard / literature: C-ITS Platform. (2016). <i>Final Report, Phase I</i> . European Commission																							
Calculation Formula: $IVCS \text{ Maturity} = \frac{\sum IVCS_i}{n}$ <p>Where: $IVCS_i$ = Maturity score of individual vehicle i n = total number of vehicles in the selected area during the specific period</p> <p>IVCS Maturity scale:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="225 1346 1331 1599"> <thead> <tr> <th>Maturity Score</th> <th>Capability</th> <th>Service example</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No digital display</td> <td>No messages to driver</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Legacy Broadcast</td> <td>Traffic Radio (RDS-TA/TMC)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Safety awareness</td> <td>Hazard warnings (Accidents/weather)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Regulatory Signage</td> <td>In vehicle sped limits / stop signs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Traffic Efficiency</td> <td>Green light timing (GLOSA) / Parking</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Full Cooperation</td> <td>Vulnerable Road User (VRU) Alerts</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Maturity Score	Capability	Service example	0	No digital display	No messages to driver	1	Legacy Broadcast	Traffic Radio (RDS-TA/TMC)	2	Safety awareness	Hazard warnings (Accidents/weather)	3	Regulatory Signage	In vehicle sped limits / stop signs	4	Traffic Efficiency	Green light timing (GLOSA) / Parking	5	Full Cooperation	Vulnerable Road User (VRU) Alerts
Maturity Score	Capability	Service example																					
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4	Traffic Efficiency	Green light timing (GLOSA) / Parking																					
5	Full Cooperation	Vulnerable Road User (VRU) Alerts																					
Data and Information Sources: Vehicle technical specifications Stationary camera videos or images																							
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Road users, automotive producers, traffic managers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																					

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Mobile Communication System</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC_TM6_2	Description: Average maturity level of messages displayed on Mobile Communication Systems (smartphones, tablets, etc.) within given area.	
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: Integer 0 – 5
Relevant standard / literature: C-ITS Platform. (2016). <i>Final Report, Phase I</i> . European Commission		
Calculation Formula: $MCS\ Maturity = \frac{\sum MCS_i}{n}$ <p>Where: MCS_i = Maturity score of individual device i n = total number of observed devices in the selected area during the specific period</p>		
MCS Maturity scale: Maturity Score	Capability	Service example
0	No Connectivity	No C-ITS application or data connection active.
1	Static Info	One-way reception of general traffic/weather via cellular.
2	Hazard Awareness	Receiving Event Messages like accidents or roadworks
3	Virtual Signage	Receiving Singage Messages like road closures
4	Contextual Info	Receiving urban info (public transit)
5	Active Cooperation	Device uploads GPS to the network to be detected by others
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Survey ▪ Telecommunication operator data 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Road users, emergency service, traffic managers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V)</h2>																						
KPI Code: SCC_TM6_3	Description: Average level of maturity of V2V communication based on the capability to exchange and process data. Ranges from basic position broadcasting to cooperative sensor perception and shared trajectory intent.																						
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: Integer 0 – 5																					
Relevant standard / literature: C-ITS Platform. (2016). <i>Final Report, Phase I</i> . European Commission																							
Calculation Formula: $V2V \text{ Maturity} = \frac{\sum V2V_i}{n}$ <p>Where: $V2V_i$ = Maturity score of individual vehicle i n = total number of vehicles in the selected area during the specific period V2V Maturity scale:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="185 1245 1345 1615"> <thead> <tr> <th>SCORE</th> <th>Capability</th> <th>Service example</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Incapable</td> <td>No hardware/software to capture data that could be sent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Autonomous</td> <td>Vehicle able to capture data (sensors) but not able to share it</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Basic Sharing</td> <td>Shares GPS and/or speed data</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Extended View</td> <td>Shares sensor information about environment</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Intent Sharing</td> <td>Shares planned trajectory and intent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Coordination</td> <td>Syncing between vehicles for manoeuvring</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			SCORE	Capability	Service example	0	Incapable	No hardware/software to capture data that could be sent	1	Autonomous	Vehicle able to capture data (sensors) but not able to share it	2	Basic Sharing	Shares GPS and/or speed data	3	Extended View	Shares sensor information about environment	4	Intent Sharing	Shares planned trajectory and intent	5	Coordination	Syncing between vehicles for manoeuvring
SCORE	Capability	Service example																					
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5	Coordination	Syncing between vehicles for manoeuvring																					
Data and Information Sources: Vehicle technical specifications Stationary camera videos or images																							
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Road users, emergency service, traffic managers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																					

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Vehicle to Infrastructure (V2I)</h2>																						
KPI Code: SCC_TM6_4	Description: Average level of maturity of Vehicle to Infrastructure (V2I/I2V) communication based on data flow and legal weight of information. Ranging from one-way broadcasts to active feedback and two-way interaction																						
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: Integer 0 – 5																					
Relevant standard / literature: C-ITS Platform. (2016). <i>Final Report, Phase I</i> . European Commission																							
Calculation Formula: $V2I \text{ Maturity} = \frac{\sum V2I_i}{n}$ <p>V2I Maturity scale:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="185 1167 1174 1554"> <thead> <tr> <th>SCORE</th> <th>Capability</th> <th>Service example</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Disconnected</td> <td>No communication</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Informative</td> <td>I2V (One-way): general traffic and weather updates</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Safety</td> <td>I2V (One-way) : Specific warnings</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Regulatory</td> <td>I2V (One-way) : Legal messages</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Active Link</td> <td>V2I (One-way out): Vehicle broadcasts its status to the road</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Cooperative</td> <td>Bidirectional: Real-time communication</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			SCORE	Capability	Service example	0	Disconnected	No communication	1	Informative	I2V (One-way): general traffic and weather updates	2	Safety	I2V (One-way) : Specific warnings	3	Regulatory	I2V (One-way) : Legal messages	4	Active Link	V2I (One-way out): Vehicle broadcasts its status to the road	5	Cooperative	Bidirectional: Real-time communication
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5	Cooperative	Bidirectional: Real-time communication																					
Data and Information Sources: Vehicle technical specifications Stationary camera videos or images Traffic operator / traffic management system																							
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Traffic managers, road users, emergency service	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																					

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: Infrastructure to infrastructure I2I																						
KPI Code: SCC.TM.6.5	Description: Level of maturity of I2I communication based on integration and automation between observed systems. Ranging from isolated local operations to a fully unified network orchestration.																						
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: Integer 0 – 5																					
Relevant standard / literature: C-ITS Platform. (2016). <i>Final Report, Phase I</i> . European Commission																							
Calculation Formula: $I2I \text{ Maturity} = \min(\text{Maturity Score})$ <p>I2I Maturity scale</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="185 1155 1345 1496"> <thead> <tr> <th>Maturity Score</th> <th>Capability</th> <th>Service example</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Isolated</td> <td>Systems operate independently</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Fragmented</td> <td>Human intervention required to share data</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Connected</td> <td>Passive: System A can access System B's data</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Integrated</td> <td>Systems exchange data automatically</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Coordinated</td> <td>Cross-systems have automated workflows</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Cooperative</td> <td>Entire network functions as a "Digital Twin"</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Maturity Score	Capability	Service example	0	Isolated	Systems operate independently	1	Fragmented	Human intervention required to share data	2	Connected	Passive: System A can access System B's data	3	Integrated	Systems exchange data automatically	4	Coordinated	Cross-systems have automated workflows	5	Cooperative	Entire network functions as a "Digital Twin"
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Data and Information Sources: Traffic operator / traffic management system																							
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Traffic managers, road users, emergency service	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																					

5.4 Infrastructure

The infrastructure (SCC_INF) category evaluates the condition of all infrastructure elements that are present in a road network. Road Condition (INF1_X) assesses the quality of pavement along with its skid resistance, shoulder condition, state of signs, markings, and delineations to give a road safety rating. Objects, Clear Zones, and Road Restraint Systems (INF2_X) measure presence, condition, density and placement of all elements of roadside to determine risk exposure. Intersections (INF3_X) evaluate geometry, control type, channelisation quality, conflict potential and level-crossing protection to assess junction safety. Vulnerable Road User's Facilities (INF4_X) measures level of protection and separation provided to pedestrians and cyclists including both along route and crossing quality. Subcategory Maintenance / Road Works (INF5_X) measures presence, extent, and impact on traffic of temporary road works via capturing affected length, speed reduction imposed and level of road closure (partial closure or full closure). Data for this category will be sourced from georeferenced video and complemented with road design specifications and documentation where necessary.

The overview of all KPIs for Infrastructure category is presented in Table 5-4. In the next paragraphs the KPI card for each criteria is provided.

Table 5-4 Overview of SCC KPIs for Infrastructure

Group	Criteria	Code	KPI
INF1	Road condition	INF1_1	Pavement Condition
		INF1_2	Contamination Impact on Skid Resistance
		INF1_3	Shoulder Condition Score
		INF1_4	Signs, Markings & Delineation Condition
		INF1_5	Condition of Road Restraint System
INF2	Objects, clear zones and road restraint systems	INF2_1	Roadside Environment and Clear zones
		INF2_2	Fixed Obstacles
		INF2_3	Distance of Obstacles from Roadside
		INF2_4	Density of Obstacles
		INF2_5	Rumble Strips
INF3	Intersections	INF3_1	Intersection type
		INF3_2	Channelisation
		INF3_3	Intersection Quality
		INF3_4	Level Crossings
INF4	Vulnerable road users' facilities	INF4_1	Vulnerable User Crossing
		INF4_2	Vulnerable User Facilities
INF5	Maintenance / road works	INF5_1	Presence & Impact of Road Works

5.4.1 Road condition

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Pavement Condition</h2>																			
KPI Code: SCC_INFI_1	Description: Evaluate pavement condition using visual inspection data based on PASER methodology and visual assessment from georeferenced video.																			
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period (e.g. annually)		Unit: Integer (1-10)																		
Relevant standard / literature: Wisconsin Transportation Information Center (2002). Pavement Surface Evaluation and Rating (PASER) Manual: Asphalt Roads. University of Wisconsin–Madison revised 2013.																				
Calculation Formula: $Pavement\ Condition = \frac{\sum(L_i \times P_i)}{\sum L_i} \times 100\%$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ P_i = PASER Segment condition score for segment i (1 – 10) ▪ L_i = Segment length (km) <p>Asphalt scoring table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="145 1294 815 1588"> <thead> <tr> <th>PASER SCORE</th> <th>Condition</th> <th>Recommended Maintenance</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>9–10</td> <td>Excellent</td> <td>None / Preventive</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7–8</td> <td>Good</td> <td>Minor maintenance</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5–6</td> <td>Fair</td> <td>Sealcoat</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3–4</td> <td>Poor</td> <td>Structural overlay</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1–2</td> <td>Very Poor</td> <td>Reconstruction</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			PASER SCORE	Condition	Recommended Maintenance	9–10	Excellent	None / Preventive	7–8	Good	Minor maintenance	5–6	Fair	Sealcoat	3–4	Poor	Structural overlay	1–2	Very Poor	Reconstruction
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7–8	Good	Minor maintenance																		
5–6	Fair	Sealcoat																		
3–4	Poor	Structural overlay																		
1–2	Very Poor	Reconstruction																		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle • Type and quantity / size of the defect are explained in the PASER Manual and considered in the Score. 																				
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Contamination Impact on Skid Resistance</h2>																										
KPI Code: SCC_INF1_2	Description: Evaluate skid resistance using visual inspection data from georeferenced video.																										
Calculation frequency: Triggered by severe weather or regular inspection		Unit: %																									
Relevant standard / literature: Not applicable																											
Calculation Formula: $\text{Contamination Index (\%)} = \frac{A_{\text{contaminated}}}{A_{\text{road,total}}} \times 100$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ $A_{\text{contaminated}}$ = area of road covered with skid reducing contaminant (m²) ▪ $A_{\text{road,total}}$ = Total area of observed road (m²) <p>Contamination Classification table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="456 1182 1426 1541"> <thead> <tr> <th>Grade</th> <th>Cont. Index (% area)</th> <th>Condition</th> <th>Interpretation</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5 – Excellent</td> <td>0 – 5 %</td> <td>Safe</td> <td>No visible contamination</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4 – Good</td> <td>5 – 15 %</td> <td>Slightly dangerous</td> <td>Small or isolated patches</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3 – Fair</td> <td>>15–30 %</td> <td>Moderately dangerous</td> <td>Several contaminated areas</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 – Poor</td> <td>>30–50 %</td> <td>Dangerous</td> <td>Large areas contaminated</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1 – Very Poor</td> <td>>50 %</td> <td>Severely dangerous</td> <td>Majority contaminated</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Grade	Cont. Index (% area)	Condition	Interpretation	5 – Excellent	0 – 5 %	Safe	No visible contamination	4 – Good	5 – 15 %	Slightly dangerous	Small or isolated patches	3 – Fair	>15–30 %	Moderately dangerous	Several contaminated areas	2 – Poor	>30–50 %	Dangerous	Large areas contaminated	1 – Very Poor	>50 %	Severely dangerous	Majority contaminated
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1 – Very Poor	>50 %	Severely dangerous	Majority contaminated																								
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle • Weather stations and weather forecast data • Contaminants include water, oil/fuel, snow, mud, loose gravel, organic matter, and dust. 																											
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																									

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Shoulder Condition Score</h2>																			
KPI Code: SCC_INF1_3	Description: Evaluate shoulder condition using visual inspection data based on PASER methodology and visual assessment from georeferenced video.																			
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period (e.g. annually)		Unit: Integer 1-5																		
Relevant standard / literature: Wisconsin Transportation Information Center (2002). Pavement Surface Evaluation and Rating (PASER) Manual: Gravel Roads., University of Wisconsin–Madison, 1989; revised 2002.																				
Calculation Formula: $\text{Shoulder Condition} = \frac{\sum(L_i \times Sh_i)}{\sum L_i}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sh_i = PASER Segment condition score for segment i (1 – 5) ▪ L_i = Segment length (km) <p>Shoulder Scoring table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="568 1205 1222 1525"> <thead> <tr> <th>PASER SCORE</th> <th>Condition</th> <th>Typical Maintenance</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Excellent</td> <td>None / Preventive</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Good</td> <td>Minor shaping or spot graveling</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Fair</td> <td>Regraveling or reshaping</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Poor</td> <td>Major reshaping</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Very Poor</td> <td>Reconstruction</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			PASER SCORE	Condition	Typical Maintenance	5	Excellent	None / Preventive	4	Good	Minor shaping or spot graveling	3	Fair	Regraveling or reshaping	2	Poor	Major reshaping	1	Very Poor	Reconstruction
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3	Fair	Regraveling or reshaping																		
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1	Very Poor	Reconstruction																		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle • For asphalted shoulder, Pavement Condition Score method is applied and rounded down to fit scale 1-5 conservatively. 																				
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Signs, Markings & Delineation Condition</h2>																															
KPI Code: SCC_INF1_4	Description: Assess the visibility, placement, and condition of road signs, markings, and delineators through visual evaluation of georeferenced video.																															
Calculation frequency / literature: For selected territory and period (e.g. annually)		Unit: Integer 0-5																														
Relevant standard: EN 1436:2018 Road marking materials, EN 12899-1:2007 Fixed, vertical road traffic signs - Part 1																																
Calculation Formula: $Composite\ SMD\ SCORE = \frac{\sum L_i \times (0.4S_i + 0.4M_i + 0.2D_i)}{\sum L_i}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ $S_i/D_i/M_i$ = Average Sign/Delineation/Marking Score for segment i (1-5) ▪ L_i = Segment length (km) <p>Signs, Markings & Delineation Scoring table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1162 965 1373"> <thead> <tr> <th>Points</th> <th>Criterion</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0-2</td> <td>Placement / Alignment</td> <td>Proper position, height, offset, or lateral alignment</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-2</td> <td>Visibility</td> <td>Not obstructed, clearly visible, reflective at night, not dirty</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-1</td> <td>Physical Condition</td> <td>Intact, not broken, faded, or missing</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Composite SMD Scoring Table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1487 976 1821"> <thead> <tr> <th>Score SMD</th> <th>Condition</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>4.5-5.0</td> <td>Excellent</td> <td>All elements visible and well placed</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.5-4.4</td> <td>Good</td> <td>Minor fading or small placement deviations</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.5-3.4</td> <td>Fair</td> <td>Moderate visibility loss / misplacement</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.5-2.4</td> <td>Poor</td> <td>Many faded or obstructed elements</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-1.4</td> <td>Very Poor</td> <td>Missing or illegible markings/signs</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Points	Criterion	Description	0-2	Placement / Alignment	Proper position, height, offset, or lateral alignment	0-2	Visibility	Not obstructed, clearly visible, reflective at night, not dirty	0-1	Physical Condition	Intact, not broken, faded, or missing	Score SMD	Condition	Description	4.5-5.0	Excellent	All elements visible and well placed	3.5-4.4	Good	Minor fading or small placement deviations	2.5-3.4	Fair	Moderate visibility loss / misplacement	1.5-2.4	Poor	Many faded or obstructed elements	0-1.4	Very Poor	Missing or illegible markings/signs
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Data and Information Sources:

- Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle

<p>Preferred direction:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↑</p>	<p>Target users:</p> <p>Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users</p>	<p>ISAD Level</p> <p>The level should be determined in line with Table 2-1.</p> <p>A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/></p>
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Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Condition of Road Restraint System</h2>																															
KPI Code: SCC_INF1_5	Description: Assess the placement, physical integrity, and surface condition of road restraint systems through visual evaluation of georeferenced video.																															
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period (e.g. annually)		Unit: Integer 0-5																														
Relevant standard / literature: EN 1317 -5:2009 Road restraint systems -- Part 5: Product requirements and evaluation of conformity for vehicle restraint systems (EN 1317-5:2007+A1:2008, Conference of European Directors of Roads (CEDR) (2018). PREMIUM – Requirements for Vehicle Restraint Systems. CEDR Call 2014.																																
Calculation Formula: $Composite\ RRS = \frac{\sum L_i \times RRS_i}{\sum L_i}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ RRS_i= Average Road Restraint System Score for segment i (0-5) ▪ L_i = Segment length (km) <p>Gravel Scoring table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1193 938 1404"> <thead> <tr> <th>Points</th> <th>Criterion</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0-2</td> <td>Placement / Alignment</td> <td>Proper height, offset, alignment with carriageway</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-2</td> <td>Physical Integrity</td> <td>No deformations, missing parts, or damage</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-1</td> <td>Surface Condition</td> <td>No corrosion, rust, dirt, or obstruction</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Composite Scoring Table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1494 949 1839"> <thead> <tr> <th>Composite Score</th> <th>Condition</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>4.5-5.0</td> <td>Excellent</td> <td>All elements visible and well placed</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.5-4.4</td> <td>Good</td> <td>Minor deviations (alignment or cosmetic defect)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.5-3.4</td> <td>Fair</td> <td>Moderate alignment or surface deterioration</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.5-2.4</td> <td>Poor</td> <td>Significant misalignment, noticeable defects</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-1.4</td> <td>Very Poor</td> <td>Major damage, missing or misplacement</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Points	Criterion	Description	0-2	Placement / Alignment	Proper height, offset, alignment with carriageway	0-2	Physical Integrity	No deformations, missing parts, or damage	0-1	Surface Condition	No corrosion, rust, dirt, or obstruction	Composite Score	Condition	Description	4.5-5.0	Excellent	All elements visible and well placed	3.5-4.4	Good	Minor deviations (alignment or cosmetic defect)	2.5-3.4	Fair	Moderate alignment or surface deterioration	1.5-2.4	Poor	Significant misalignment, noticeable defects	0-1.4	Very Poor	Major damage, missing or misplacement
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0-1.4	Very Poor	Major damage, missing or misplacement																														

Data and Information Sources:

- Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle

<p>Preferred direction:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↑</p>	<p>Target users:</p> <p>Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users</p>	<p>ISAD Level</p> <p>A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
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5.4.2 Objects, clear zones and road restraint systems

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Roadside Environment and Clear zones</h2>																															
KPI Code: SCC.INF.2.1	Description: Assess the condition and safety of roadside areas and clear zones through visual evaluation of obstacles, vegetation, and recoverable slopes from georeferenced video.																															
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period (e.g. annually)		Unit: Integer 0-5																														
Relevant standard / literature: American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) (2011). Roadside Design Guide (4th ed.). Washington, D.C.																																
Calculation Formula: $\text{Composite RCS} = \frac{\sum L_i \times RCS_i}{\sum L_i}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ RCS_i = Roadside Condition Score (0-5) for segment i ▪ L_i = Segment length (km) <p>Roadside Environment and Clear Zones Scoring table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1352 1019 1565"> <thead> <tr> <th>Points</th> <th>Criterion</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0-2</td> <td>Clear Zone Condition</td> <td>Free from obstacles, vegetation, or debris</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-2</td> <td>Slope / Traversability</td> <td>Smooth, recoverable slope without steep drop-offs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-1</td> <td>Obstacle Management</td> <td>Safe placement of roadside accessories</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Composite RCS Scoring table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1644 1099 1917"> <thead> <tr> <th>RCS Score</th> <th>Condition</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>4.5-5.0</td> <td>Excellent</td> <td>Clear zone unobstructed, traversable, no hazards</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.5-4.4</td> <td>Good</td> <td>Minor vegetation or slope/obstacle issues</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.5-3.4</td> <td>Fair</td> <td>Noticeable obstructions or uneven slopes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.5-2.4</td> <td>Poor</td> <td>Significant obstacles or unsafe slopes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-1.4</td> <td>Very Poor</td> <td>Major obstructions, restricted traversability</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Points	Criterion	Description	0-2	Clear Zone Condition	Free from obstacles, vegetation, or debris	0-2	Slope / Traversability	Smooth, recoverable slope without steep drop-offs	0-1	Obstacle Management	Safe placement of roadside accessories	RCS Score	Condition	Description	4.5-5.0	Excellent	Clear zone unobstructed, traversable, no hazards	3.5-4.4	Good	Minor vegetation or slope/obstacle issues	2.5-3.4	Fair	Noticeable obstructions or uneven slopes	1.5-2.4	Poor	Significant obstacles or unsafe slopes	0-1.4	Very Poor	Major obstructions, restricted traversability
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1.5-2.4	Poor	Significant obstacles or unsafe slopes																														
0-1.4	Very Poor	Major obstructions, restricted traversability																														

<p>Data and Information Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle 		
<p>Preferred direction:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↑</p>	<p>Target users:</p> <p>Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users</p>	<p>ISAD Level</p> <p>A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Fixed Obstacles</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC.INF.2.2	Description: Counts the number and type of fixed roadside obstacles detected through visual assessment of georeferenced video.	
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: Integer, descriptive type
Relevant standard / literature: American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) (2011). Roadside Design Guide (4th ed.). Washington, D.C.		
Calculation Formula: $N_{obstacle,type}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $N_{obstacle,type}$ = Total number of detected fixed obstacles along the analysed section, per type 		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Distance of Obstacles from Roadside</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC.INF.2.3	Description: Assess the distance of obstacles from roadside through visual evaluation of georeferenced video.	
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: Integer
Relevant standard / literature: American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) (2011). Roadside Design Guide (4th ed.). Washington, D.C.		
Calculation Formula: $D_{obstacle}$ Where: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ $D_{obstacle}$ = measured distance (in meters) from pavement edge to each obstacle 		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle • Automated or manual measurement tools for lateral offset 		
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Density of Obstacles</h2>	
KPI Code: SCC.INF.2.4	Description: Calculate the number of fixed obstacles per segment of road to quantify roadside exposure and safety risk.	
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period		Unit: Obstacles/km
Relevant standard / literature: American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) (2011). Roadside Design Guide (4th ed.). Washington, D.C.		
Calculation Formula: $\text{Obstacle density} = \frac{N_{\text{obstacle,type}}}{L_{\text{road}}}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • L_{road} = total length of analysed road (km) • $N_{\text{obstacle,type}}$ = total number of detected fixed obstacles along the analysed section, per type 		
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregated data from INF2.2 (Fixed Obstacles) • Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle 		
Preferred direction: ↓	Target users: Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Rumble Strips</h2>																															
KPI Code: SCC_INF2_5	Description: Evaluate placement, visibility, and physical condition of rumble strips through visual assessment.																															
Calculation frequency: For selected territory, update triggered by change		Unit: Integer 0-5																														
Relevant standard / literature: American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) (2011). Roadside Design Guide (4th ed.). Washington, D.C.																																
Calculation Formula: $Composite\ RS = \frac{\sum L_i \times RS_i}{\sum L_i}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RS_i = Rumble Strip Score (0-5) for segment i • L_i = Length of segment i <p>Rumble road strips Scoring table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1128 938 1312"> <thead> <tr> <th>Points</th> <th>Criterion</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0-2</td> <td>Existence</td> <td>Installed where required</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-2</td> <td>Completeness</td> <td>Full length (2 pts); partial (1 pt)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-1</td> <td>Design Conformance</td> <td>Within tolerance (2 pts); slight deviation (1 pt)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Composite RS Scoring:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1357 938 1603"> <thead> <tr> <th>RS Score</th> <th>Condition</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>4.5-5.0</td> <td>Excellent</td> <td>Fully present, meets design</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.5-4.4</td> <td>Good</td> <td>Minor gaps or wear</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.5-3.4</td> <td>Fair</td> <td>Partial or uneven layout</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.5-2.4</td> <td>Poor</td> <td>Incomplete or inconsistent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-1.4</td> <td>Very Poor</td> <td>Missing or degraded</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Points	Criterion	Description	0-2	Existence	Installed where required	0-2	Completeness	Full length (2 pts); partial (1 pt)	0-1	Design Conformance	Within tolerance (2 pts); slight deviation (1 pt)	RS Score	Condition	Description	4.5-5.0	Excellent	Fully present, meets design	3.5-4.4	Good	Minor gaps or wear	2.5-3.4	Fair	Partial or uneven layout	1.5-2.4	Poor	Incomplete or inconsistent	0-1.4	Very Poor	Missing or degraded
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0-1.4	Very Poor	Missing or degraded																														
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle • 																																
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																														

5.4.3 Intersections

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2>Intersection type</h2>													
KPI Code: SCC_INF3_1	Description: Classifies the intersection based on 3 main categories: geometry, level and type of control.													
Calculation frequency: For selected territory and period, update triggered by change		Unit: Category												
Relevant standard / literature: National Association of City Transportation Officials (NACTO) (2013a). Urban Intersection Design Guide. Washington, D.C.: Island Press.														
Calculation Formula: Not applicable, KPI is descriptive, see table below. Classification categories: <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1093 852 1391"> <thead> <tr> <th>Criterion</th> <th>Categories</th> <th>Notes</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Geometry</td> <td>T-junction, Y-junction, 4-leg (cross), multi-leg</td> <td>Shape / number of arms</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level</td> <td>At-grade, Grade-separated (overpass, underpass)</td> <td>Based on vertical alignment</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Control Type</td> <td>Uncontrolled, Priority (signs), Signalized, Roundabout</td> <td>Visual control element</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Criterion	Categories	Notes	Geometry	T-junction, Y-junction, 4-leg (cross), multi-leg	Shape / number of arms	Level	At-grade, Grade-separated (overpass, underpass)	Based on vertical alignment	Control Type	Uncontrolled, Priority (signs), Signalized, Roundabout	Visual control element
Criterion	Categories	Notes												
Geometry	T-junction, Y-junction, 4-leg (cross), multi-leg	Shape / number of arms												
Level	At-grade, Grade-separated (overpass, underpass)	Based on vertical alignment												
Control Type	Uncontrolled, Priority (signs), Signalized, Roundabout	Visual control element												
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle • GIS road network and intersection mapping layer 														
Preferred direction: n/a	Target users: Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level The level should be determined in line with Table 2-1. A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/>												

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: Channelisation																			
KPI Code: SCC_INF3_2	Description: Assess whether channelisation exists at intersections and identify condition and whether it is physical or painted.																			
Calculation frequency: Based on the agreed period or triggered by change		Unit: Integer 0-5																		
Relevant standard / literature: American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) (2018). A Policy on Geometric Design of Highways and Streets (7th ed.). Washington, D.C.																				
Calculation Formula: $Composite\ CHS = \frac{\sum L_i \times CHS_i}{\sum L_i}$ Where: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CHS_i= Channelisation Score (0-5) for segment i • L_i= Length of segment i Channelisation Scoring table:																				
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Points</th> <th>Criterion</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Existence</td> <td>Channelisation present at the intersection</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-2</td> <td>Type</td> <td>Physical (2 pts) or painted (1 pt)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-2</td> <td>Condition / Visibility</td> <td>Visible and functional (2); faded (1); not functional (0)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Points	Criterion	Description	1	Existence	Channelisation present at the intersection	0-2	Type	Physical (2 pts) or painted (1 pt)	0-2	Condition / Visibility	Visible and functional (2); faded (1); not functional (0)						
Points	Criterion	Description																		
1	Existence	Channelisation present at the intersection																		
0-2	Type	Physical (2 pts) or painted (1 pt)																		
0-2	Condition / Visibility	Visible and functional (2); faded (1); not functional (0)																		
Composition scoring:																				
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>CHS Score</th> <th>Condition</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>4.5-5.0</td> <td>Excellent</td> <td>Clear and functional physical channelisation</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.5-4.4</td> <td>Good</td> <td>Painted and fully visible</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.5-3.4</td> <td>Fair</td> <td>Minor wear or partial visibility</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.5-2.4</td> <td>Poor</td> <td>Damaged or unclear</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-1.4</td> <td>Very Poor</td> <td>Absent or not visible</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			CHS Score	Condition	Description	4.5-5.0	Excellent	Clear and functional physical channelisation	3.5-4.4	Good	Painted and fully visible	2.5-3.4	Fair	Minor wear or partial visibility	1.5-2.4	Poor	Damaged or unclear	0-1.4	Very Poor	Absent or not visible
CHS Score	Condition	Description																		
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3.5-4.4	Good	Painted and fully visible																		
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1.5-2.4	Poor	Damaged or unclear																		
0-1.4	Very Poor	Absent or not visible																		

Data and Information Sources:

- Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle

<p>Preferred direction:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↑</p>	<p>Target users:</p> <p>Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users</p>	<p>ISAD Level</p> <p>The level should be determined in line with Table 2-1.</p> <p>A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/></p>
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Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Intersection Quality</h2>																			
KPI Code: SCC.INF.3.3	Description: Evaluate the design quality of intersections based on the number and type of potential vehicle conflict points.																			
Calculation frequency: For the agreed period or triggered by change		Unit: Integer 0-1																		
Relevant standard / literature: American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) (2018). A Policy on Geometric Design of Highways and Streets (7th ed.). Washington, D.C.																				
Calculation Formula: $\text{Intersection Quality Score} = 1 - \frac{C_i}{C_{\max(\text{legs,lanes})}}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C_i = Actual number of conflict points for the given intersection design • $C_{\max(\text{legs,lanes})}$ = Theoretical maximum number of conflict points possible for an uncontrolled at-grade intersection with the same number of legs and lanes 																				
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle <p>Composite Score:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1391 922 1720"> <thead> <tr> <th>KPI Value</th> <th>Condition</th> <th>Meaning</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0.80–1.00</td> <td>Excellent</td> <td>Very safe, low-conflict design (e.g. roundabout, grade-separated)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0.60–0.79</td> <td>Good</td> <td>Low to moderate conflicts</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0.40–0.59</td> <td>Fair</td> <td>Typical signalized or priority intersection</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0.20–0.39</td> <td>Poor</td> <td>High number of conflicts, suboptimal design</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0.00–0.19</td> <td>Very Poor</td> <td>Fully uncontrolled, conflict-heavy layout</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <div style="text-align: right; margin-top: 20px;"> </div>			KPI Value	Condition	Meaning	0.80–1.00	Excellent	Very safe, low-conflict design (e.g. roundabout, grade-separated)	0.60–0.79	Good	Low to moderate conflicts	0.40–0.59	Fair	Typical signalized or priority intersection	0.20–0.39	Poor	High number of conflicts, suboptimal design	0.00–0.19	Very Poor	Fully uncontrolled, conflict-heavy layout
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0.00–0.19	Very Poor	Fully uncontrolled, conflict-heavy layout																		
Preferred direction: <p style="text-align: center;">↑</p>	Target users: Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Level Crossings</h2>																																		
KPI Code: SCC_INF3_4	Description: Assess the presence and functionality of visual and physical protection systems at level crossings using georeferenced video.																																		
Calculation frequency: For the agreed period or triggered by change		Unit: Integer 0-5																																	
Relevant standard / literature: U.S. Federal Highway Administration (FHWA) (2019). Highway Rail Crossing Handbook (3rd ed.). U.S. Department of Transportation.																																			
Calculation Formula: $Composite\ LCS = \frac{\sum L_i \times LCS_i}{\sum L_i}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ LCS_i = Level Crossing Score for section i ▪ L_i = Segment length (km) <p>Level Crossing Scoring table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1205 938 1391"> <thead> <tr> <th>Points</th> <th>Criterion</th> <th>States</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0-2</td> <td>Ramp / barrier</td> <td>None, manual, automatic</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-1</td> <td>Audio Signalization</td> <td>None, present</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-1</td> <td>Approach Signalization</td> <td>None, present</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0-1</td> <td>Physical markings</td> <td>None, present</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Composite score:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1485 975 1753"> <thead> <tr> <th>LCS Score</th> <th>Condition</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>4.5 – 5.0</td> <td>Excellent</td> <td>Fully equipped and operational</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3.5 – 4.4</td> <td>Good</td> <td>Minor deficiencies</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2.5 – 3.4</td> <td>Fair</td> <td>Missing one safety feature</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.5 – 2.4</td> <td>Poor</td> <td>Lacking key features</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0 – 1.4</td> <td>Very Poor</td> <td>Unprotected crossing</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Points	Criterion	States	0-2	Ramp / barrier	None, manual, automatic	0-1	Audio Signalization	None, present	0-1	Approach Signalization	None, present	0-1	Physical markings	None, present	LCS Score	Condition	Description	4.5 – 5.0	Excellent	Fully equipped and operational	3.5 – 4.4	Good	Minor deficiencies	2.5 – 3.4	Fair	Missing one safety feature	1.5 – 2.4	Poor	Lacking key features	0 – 1.4	Very Poor	Unprotected crossing
Points	Criterion	States																																	
0-2	Ramp / barrier	None, manual, automatic																																	
0-1	Audio Signalization	None, present																																	
0-1	Approach Signalization	None, present																																	
0-1	Physical markings	None, present																																	
LCS Score	Condition	Description																																	
4.5 – 5.0	Excellent	Fully equipped and operational																																	
3.5 – 4.4	Good	Minor deficiencies																																	
2.5 – 3.4	Fair	Missing one safety feature																																	
1.5 – 2.4	Poor	Lacking key features																																	
0 – 1.4	Very Poor	Unprotected crossing																																	

Data and Information Sources:

- Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle

<p>Preferred direction:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↑</p>	<p>Target users:</p> <p>Infrastructure and traffic managers, road users</p>	<p>ISAD Level</p> <p>The level should be determined in line with Table 2-1.</p> <p>A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/></p>
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5.4.4 Vulnerable road users' facilities

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Vulnerable User Crossing</h2>																						
KPI Code: SCC_INF4_1	Description: Evaluate the quality and safety design of pedestrian and cyclist crossing, based on visibility, protection and separation level from visual inspection.																						
Calculation frequency: Annually or based on the need		Unit: Integer 0-5																					
Relevant standard / literature: National Association of City Transportation Officials (NACTO) (2013a). Urban Intersection Design Guide. Washington, D.C.: Island Press.																							
Calculation Formula: $VUC\ Score = \frac{\sum VUC_{i,type}}{\sum i}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ $VUC_{i,type}$ = Vulnerable user facilities score for segment i ▪ L_i = Segment length (km) <p>Vulnerable User Facilities Scoring table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="164 1178 1430 1451"> <thead> <tr> <th>Score</th> <th>Facility Type / Condition</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>None</td> <td>Users move on the roadway without protection</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Painted edge or lane on roadway</td> <td>Minimal separation from traffic</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Shared use sidewalk or path (pedestrian + cyclist)</td> <td>Mixed traffic between modes, no buffer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Dedicated lane directly beside traffic</td> <td>Standard facility with curb or lane marking only</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Buffered or partially separated facility</td> <td>Physical buffer, green strip, or parking protection</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Fully separated or grade-separated facility</td> <td>Complete separation, off-road or independent path</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Score	Facility Type / Condition	Description	0	None	Users move on the roadway without protection	1	Painted edge or lane on roadway	Minimal separation from traffic	2	Shared use sidewalk or path (pedestrian + cyclist)	Mixed traffic between modes, no buffer	3	Dedicated lane directly beside traffic	Standard facility with curb or lane marking only	4	Buffered or partially separated facility	Physical buffer, green strip, or parking protection	5	Fully separated or grade-separated facility	Complete separation, off-road or independent path
Score	Facility Type / Condition	Description																					
0	None	Users move on the roadway without protection																					
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4	Buffered or partially separated facility	Physical buffer, green strip, or parking protection																					
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Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle 																							
Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Vulnerable road users, road users, traffic and infrastructure managers	ISAD Level The level should be determined in line with Table 2-1. A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/>																					

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: <h2 style="text-align: center;">Vulnerable User Facilities</h2>																						
KPI Code: SCC_INF4_2	Description: Evaluate the quality protection, and separation of pedestrian or cyclist facilities based on visual assessment from georeferenced video.																						
Calculation frequency: Annually or based on the need		Unit: Integer 0-5																					
Relevant standard / literature: National Association of City Transportation Officials (NACTO) (2013b). Urban Street Design Guide. Washington, D.C.: Island Press.																							
Calculation Formula: $VUF\ Score = \frac{\sum VUF_{i,type}}{\sum L_i}$ <p>Where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ $VUC_{i,type}$ = Vulnerable user Crossing score for crossing i ▪ i = Number of crossings examined <p>Vulnerable User Crossing Scoring table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1160 1254 1453"> <thead> <tr> <th>Score</th> <th>Crossing Type / Condition</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No marked crossing</td> <td>Users cross uncontrolled, no visual cues</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Basic markings only</td> <td>Painted crossing, no physical elements</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Marked + signage</td> <td>Crosswalk with advance warning or yield signage</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Signalized or raised</td> <td>Controlled crossing or speed-reducing design</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Physically protected</td> <td>Refuge island, curb extensions, or buffer zone</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Grade-separated</td> <td>Overpass or underpass crossing, no traffic conflict</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Score	Crossing Type / Condition	Description	0	No marked crossing	Users cross uncontrolled, no visual cues	1	Basic markings only	Painted crossing, no physical elements	2	Marked + signage	Crosswalk with advance warning or yield signage	3	Signalized or raised	Controlled crossing or speed-reducing design	4	Physically protected	Refuge island, curb extensions, or buffer zone	5	Grade-separated	Overpass or underpass crossing, no traffic conflict
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Preferred direction: ↑	Target users: Vulnerable road users, road users, traffic and infrastructure managers	ISAD Level A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																					

5.4.5 Maintenance / road works

Perspective: Safety Criteria Catalogue	KPI: Presence & Impact of Road Works													
KPI Code: SCC_INF5_1	Description: Evaluate presence of road works, to what extent they impact traffic (full or partial closure) and what are the imposed speed limits.													
Calculation frequency: Triggered by Road Works event		Unit: Type, location, duration												
Relevant standard / literature: National Road Safety Law														
Calculation Formula: Not applicable, KPI is descriptive Road works classification table: <table border="1" data-bbox="165 1055 1353 1352"> <thead> <tr> <th>Criterion</th> <th>Categories</th> <th>Notes</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Work Zone Type</td> <td>Full Closure, Partial Closure, Maintenance Under Flow, None</td> <td>Defines the level of accessibility through the work zone (complete detour, lane reduction, or open flow).</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Speed Limit Condition</td> <td>Reduced, Unchanged, Not Visible</td> <td>Identifies whether a temporary lower limit is enforced within the work zone.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Work Zone Length</td> <td>Short (< 500 m), Medium (500 m – 2 km), Long (> 2 km)</td> <td>Approximate length of the affected section based on visual assessment or measurement.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Criterion	Categories	Notes	Work Zone Type	Full Closure, Partial Closure, Maintenance Under Flow, None	Defines the level of accessibility through the work zone (complete detour, lane reduction, or open flow).	Speed Limit Condition	Reduced, Unchanged, Not Visible	Identifies whether a temporary lower limit is enforced within the work zone.	Work Zone Length	Short (< 500 m), Medium (500 m – 2 km), Long (> 2 km)	Approximate length of the affected section based on visual assessment or measurement.
Criterion	Categories	Notes												
Work Zone Type	Full Closure, Partial Closure, Maintenance Under Flow, None	Defines the level of accessibility through the work zone (complete detour, lane reduction, or open flow).												
Speed Limit Condition	Reduced, Unchanged, Not Visible	Identifies whether a temporary lower limit is enforced within the work zone.												
Work Zone Length	Short (< 500 m), Medium (500 m – 2 km), Long (> 2 km)	Approximate length of the affected section based on visual assessment or measurement.												
Data and Information Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure Management Data (maintenance planning data) • Traffic regulation plan • Georeferenced video / images from camera fixed or mounted on the vehicle 														
Preferred direction: n/a	Target users: Vulnerable road users, road users, traffic and infrastructure managers	ISAD Level The level should be determined in line with Table 2-1. A <input type="checkbox"/> B <input type="checkbox"/> C <input type="checkbox"/> D <input type="checkbox"/> E <input type="checkbox"/> n/a <input type="checkbox"/>												

6 Conclusion and Outlook

The analysis of European road safety legislative and policy frameworks provides an important contextual baseline for the iDriving project. Across EU Member States, there is strong convergence around the Safe System approach and the EU Vision Zero objective of reducing road fatalities and serious injuries by 50% by 2030. This shared policy orientation supports iDriving's role as a practical, data-driven enabler of Vision Zero implementation on secondary and urban road networks.

In response, iDriving defines an enhanced Safety Criteria Catalogue (SCC) as a core methodological framework to support the evaluation and deployment of digital road safety solutions. The SCC is structured around four interrelated categories: Road Users, Vehicles, Traffic Management and Communication, and Infrastructure, and is grounded in existing EU standards, policy frameworks, and the outcomes of previous projects such as BASELINE and INFRAMIX.

For the Road Users category, the SCC adopts and builds upon the BASELINE project framework, which identifies eight key domains for assessing road user safety, including speeding, seatbelt and child restraint use, protective equipment, alcohol impairment, mobile device distraction, vehicle safety, infrastructure, and post-crash care. These domains are directly relevant to iDriving use cases, particularly in urban and rural environments with high exposure of Vulnerable Road Users. For the remaining categories, Vehicles, Traffic Management and Communication, and Infrastructure, the SCC draws on relevant standards, the ISAD classification system, and the integration of digital and connected technologies for monitoring, data collection, and communication.

Within the iDriving framework, safety criteria are operationalised through clearly defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), each supported by one or more measurable indicators. Continuous data streams from iDriving tools—including sensor-based infrastructure monitoring, AI-based defect detection, and real-time driver alert systems—are translated into KPIs tailored to secondary and urban road networks. This enables a direct link between high-level safety objectives and operational data generated within the iDriving platform.

A key innovation of the iDriving SCC is its emphasis on “leading” indicators that support proactive and preventive safety management. Unlike traditional approaches relying primarily on “lagging” crash statistics, the SCC combines the Safe System approach with continuous monitoring, AI-driven risk detection, and near-real-time alerts. This allows early identification of hazardous infrastructure conditions and risky behaviours, supporting timely interventions before crashes occur and reinforcing the preventive ambition of Vision Zero.

The SCC and its associated dynamic KPI monitoring framework will be validated across six iDriving pilot sites, enabling assessment of the real-world impacts of digital safety innovations in diverse traffic, infrastructure, and governance contexts.

This validation will also support evaluation of the transferability and scalability of the methodology. Future work within iDriving will focus on deeper integration with city-level digital twins to enable predictive safety simulations, further exploitation of use-case data for methodological validation, and closer alignment with EU-level KPI definitions and harmonised data protocols to ensure interoperability and policy relevance.

Overall, the enhanced iDriving Safety Criteria Catalogue represents a central methodological contribution of the project. By linking standardised safety criteria with continuous digital monitoring and AI-driven analysis, it provides a practical framework for transforming passive road safety monitoring into proactive, real-time safety management. In doing so, iDriving directly supports Vision Zero implementation and offers a transferable approach to improving safety outcomes—particularly for vulnerable road users—on Europe’s secondary and urban road networks.

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iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/07/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01 **Total cost:** € 4,998,733.75 **Coordinator:** Ethniko Kentro Erevnas kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (CERTH)

iDriving Consortium

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